

iNEST CCI - Final report

From Pre-Acceleration to Acceleration: Evidence from the iNEST CCI Entrepreneurial Talent Program in North-Eastern Italy (2023–2025)

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Abstract

Innovation ecosystems increasingly rely on structured pre-acceleration and acceleration programs to transform research-based ideas into viable ventures. Within the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), the iNEST Cross-Cutting Activity 1 (CC1) was designed to engage entrepreneurial talent across nine universities in North-Eastern Italy and to channel promising projects into a shared Acceleration program. This report provides a systematic assessment of two full CC1 cycles (2023–2025), addressing three questions: how the Pre-Acceleration pipeline operated and which profiles it mobilised; which factors predicted access to the Acceleration phase; and which success patterns emerged during and after Acceleration.

The analysis draws on a mixed-methods design combining descriptive statistics on 349 applications, inferential techniques (Fisher's exact tests and logistic regression) to identify critical selection drivers, and qualitative evidence from open-ended questionnaires and participant feedback on the 32 accelerated teams.

Results show that the selection process systematically rewarded projects displaying structural maturity, namely medium-sized teams (3–5 members), complementary technical-scientific and managerial competences, and the presence of technological or intellectual property assets. Sectoral orientation was also decisive: Smart Industries and Health Tech & Services projects were consistently favoured, whereas Creative Industries and other non-technological initiatives were penalised, pointing to possible tech-centric and fundability-driven biases.

During Acceleration, teams achieved the greatest progress in organisational consolidation and validation capacity, while advances in networking and fundraising remained more limited, indicating a need for stronger support on external linkages and investment readiness. Overall, the findings suggest that CC1 effectively strengthened the organisational and technical readiness of research-based start-ups and that the initiative generated value for the multi-regional innovation ecosystem by establishing shared processes, cross-university coordination mechanisms, and new connections with industrial and financial stakeholders. Yet, the analysis also revealed structural limitations of a time-boxed acceleration model for heterogeneous cohorts and that future iterations should refine selection criteria, differentiate support tracks by sector and maturity level, and better balance fundability with inclusiveness in early-stage innovation support.

Keywords

iNEST CC1; entrepreneurial ecosystems; pre-acceleration; acceleration programs; selection criteria; research-based start-ups; innovation policy; Italy / PNRR

Introduction

Over the past decade, public bodies and policy makers have increasingly recognised innovation as a key driver of competitiveness and sustainable development. This growing awareness has translated into stronger institutional attention towards start-ups and entrepreneurial initiatives, especially those emerging from universities and research centres.

Innovation is therefore understood not merely as a technological outcome but as a systemic process that involves higher education institutions, territorial actors, and private enterprises working together to translate scientific knowledge into market applications.

Within this evolving landscape, the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) has acted as a catalyst, promoting large-scale, interconnected initiatives aimed at bridging research and innovation.

Among these, the *iNEST* (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem) project represents a coordinated effort among nine universities in North-Eastern Italy to identify promising ideas and support their transformation into viable ventures. The Cross Cutting Activity 1 (CC1) - dedicated to Entrepreneurial Talent Engagement, Pre-Acceleration, Acceleration, and Fundraising - constitutes a distinctive experiment in shared governance, aligning diverse institutional competencies through a common framework for scouting, evaluation, and start-up development.

The *iNEST CC1* initiative has materialised through two complete cycles of Pre-Acceleration and Acceleration programs carried out between 2023 and 2025, involving over three hundred applicants and thirty start-ups selected for structured support activities.

Each cycle combined decentralised scouting within nine university Spokes with a centralised process of evaluation, coaching, and monitoring, testing an integrated model of entrepreneurial pipeline management at multi-regional scale.

At the conclusion of these two rounds, a substantial body of operational data and qualitative evidence became available; however, a systematic synthesis of what was done, how it was implemented, and what tangible results were achieved was still lacking.

This report seeks to fill that gap by addressing three interrelated research questions that reflect the logical sequence of the CC1 process itself.

First, how did the Pre-Acceleration pipeline operate across the nine Spokes, and which profiles of talents and ideas were most effectively mobilised? Understanding this step is essential to assess the inclusiveness and efficiency of the scouting model adopted.

Second, which team, project, and contextual characteristics most strongly influenced admission to the Acceleration phase? This question helps identify the resource combinations - technological, organisational, and human - that evaluators implicitly rewarded, shedding light on factors that best predict the admission to the Acceleration phase.

Third, what success factors and progress indicators characterised the performance of the accelerated teams during and after the program? Exploring this dimension allows us to connect selection patterns with subsequent outcomes, offering an integrated view of program effectiveness and learning across rounds.

The structure of the report reflects these three questions:

- Chapter 1 analyses the functioning of the Pre-Acceleration pipeline,
- Chapter 2 investigates the determinants of admission to Acceleration
- Chapter 3 examines the trajectories and performance of the accelerated teams.

The analysis relies on a mixed-methods design, articulated along the three research questions introduced above. Each question required a distinct methodological approach consistent with its analytical purpose and data structure.

For the **first research question**, we employed *descriptive statistics* to portray the composition of the applicant pool and the overall functioning of the Pre-Acceleration pipeline. This quantitative overview illustrates how talents and ideas were distributed across the nine Spokes and highlights the main characteristics of the projects that entered the program.

For the **second research question**, which examines the determinants of admission to the Acceleration phase, we adopted an *inferential approach*. Specifically, we conducted Fisher's exact tests to explore bivariate associations between categorical variables and selection outcomes, followed by *logistic regression models* to assess the joint influence of technological, organisational, and human-capital factors.

For the **third research question**, focused on success factors during and after the Acceleration phase, we applied a *qualitative methodology* based on open-ended questionnaires and participants' feedback. This allowed us to interpret the perceived effects of the program, the areas of improvement identified by the teams, and the broader lessons learned across rounds.

Together, these complementary methods provide a coherent analytical framework: descriptive evidence to map the ecosystem, inferential analysis to identify selection drivers, and qualitative interpretation to understand post-acceleration outcomes. This triangulation integrates numerical trends with experiential insights, ensuring both analytical depth and contextual understanding.

Our analysis yields three main results.

One, the selection process within CCI systematically rewarded projects displaying structural maturity, namely medium-sized teams (3–5 members), clear technological assets, and managerial or scientific competence complementarity.

Two, sectoral alignment mattered significantly: projects in *Smart Industries* and *Health Tech & Services* consistently outperformed those in *Creative Industries* or non-technological domains, reflecting both strategic priorities and possible evaluation biases.

Three, during the Acceleration phase, the strongest progress was observed in organisational consolidation and validation capacity, whereas advancements in networking and fundraising remained more limited, suggesting the need for enhanced support mechanisms in those areas.

These findings collectively indicate that CCI has been effective in building organisational and technical readiness among research-based startups, yet future iterations should aim to strengthen external linkages and investment preparedness.

This report makes three main contributions.

From a **methodological** perspective, it offers one of the first systematic assessments of a large-scale, multi-institutional acceleration framework implemented under the Italian *PNRR*, combining descriptive, inferential, and qualitative evidence. The integration of statistical analysis with field-based insights demonstrates the usefulness of mixed-method approaches for evaluating complex innovation ecosystems, where both measurable outcomes and emergent dynamics must be captured.

From a **theoretical and analytical** standpoint, the report contributes to the broader debate on innovation and entrepreneurship by showing how decentralised Pre-Acceleration mechanisms can be effectively coordinated through shared methodologies while preserving local specificities. The findings enrich the understanding of how resource configurations, team structures, and institutional settings shape early-stage venture development within public-academic partnerships.

Finally, from a **policy and operational** viewpoint, the report provides evidence-based recommendations for future innovation programs. It highlights the importance of balancing efficiency and inclusivity in selection processes, strengthening post-acceleration support for fundraising and networking, and designing differentiated pathways for projects with varying degrees of maturity or sectoral orientation. These insights aim to inform policymakers, ecosystem managers, and university stakeholders involved in the design of next-generation acceleration frameworks.

The remainder of the report is structured as follows.

Chapter 1 describes the talent engagement and Pre-Acceleration pipeline, highlighting the methodological design and main characteristics of the applicant pool.

Chapter 2 identifies the critical factors influencing access to the Acceleration program through both bivariate and multivariate analyses, discussing their implications for selection fairness and program design.

Chapter 3 examines success patterns during and after the Acceleration phase, using a multidimensional framework of organisational, technological, and financial outcomes. Finally, the concluding section summarises the main findings, discusses their limitations, and outlines possible directions for future research and policy learning within the iNEST ecosystem.

1. The CCI entrepreneurial talent engagement pipeline

1.1. The Pre-Acceleration process

Within the design of an innovation ecosystem for the generation and development of research start-ups and spin-offs, it is considered strategic to favor a transversal action to all Spokes, characterised by:

- a centralised management of the Acceleration & Fundraising phases
- a decentralised, yet coordinated, management of the Pre-Acceleration phase, as a course of action entrusted to the individual Spokes to generate and select the innovative ideas.

Decentralised management of the Pre-Acceleration allows a closer contact with the neo-entrepreneurs-to-be (students, PhDs, researchers, etc.), while the coordination allows reaching economics of replication through methodologies and technological platforms applicable to all Spokes, starting from the best cases of each university.

For this purpose some Key Standardised Elements were developed to promote consistent and coordinated actions, methodologies, and results. The Key Standardised Elements were:

- a **Framework**: the result of the capitalisation of successful practices and knowledge of the Spokes, it ensured to offer the same value to all the pre-accelerated ideas;
- b) **educational materials**: references and documentation for all applicants;
- c) **Scouting Specialists**: appointed by each Spoke, they were responsible for the first identification of innovative ideas, research projects and early stage start-ups potentially interesting for the general objectives of the project.

The **framework** consisted of a scouting system and an evaluation system, specifically designed for iNEST CCI, providing a common process and shared tools to the 9 Spokes while enabling personalised implementation to accommodate Spokes specificities (especially in the target engagement activities). The Pre-Acceleration process can be summarised in the following stages:

Stage	Main actors	Centralised / Decentralised	Target n. of ideas	Stage description
Target engagement and scouting	Scouting Specialists, Scouting Officer and Assistant Scouting Officers	Decentralised	10 + per Spoke	- broad engagement via events and Calls for ideas ("fishing" scouting approach) - targeted engagement actions ("hunting" scouting approach)
First application form (Open Call)	Applicants	Decentralised	10+ per Spoke	applicants fill in a simple, short form to describe their idea / project
Online entrepreneurial training	Program Leader, applicants	Centralised	10+ per Spoke	applicants are given access to a selection of reviewed international benchmarks of entrepreneurial education. In addition they are provided with a custom video guide on the preparation of a solid pitch deck
Pre-screening	Scouting Specialists (SS)	Decentralised	From 10+ per Spoke to 8+ per Spoke	considering basic viability of the ideas for the CCI initiative, each SS selects about 8 applications (out of their 10+) that proceed to the following stage

Stage	Main actors	Centralised / Decentralised	Target n. of ideas	Stage description
Selection Form	Applicants	Centralised	8+ per Spoke	applicants fill in a structured form to present their idea and their team, also uploading a pitch deck developed using a standard template (created by the CCI team)
Screening	Scouting Specialists and their supervisors	Decentralised	From 8+ per Spoke to 4+ per Spoke	the SS, together with their supervisors (members of the CCI Committee), review the 8+ applications collected by their Spoke, evaluate them quantitatively using a common set of criteria and select the 4+ ideas that access the following stage
Committee evaluation	CCI Committee, Program Leader, Program Manager	Centralised	From about 40 to about 30 ideas / start-ups	the CCI Committee members review the SS's quantitative evaluations and determine the 30 most promising ideas/start-ups that are admitted to the Selection Day
Selection Day	Applicants	Centralised	30-32 ideas / start-ups	admitted applicants present their project through a 5 min pitch + 5 min Q&A time
Selection Day	CCI Committee, Program Leader, Progr. Manager, External Jury (in round 2)	Centralised	30-32 ideas / start-ups	the CCI Committee further reviews the evaluations, based on pitches and Q&As; the External Jury evaluates the ideas / start-ups using a simplified set of criteria. The weight of the External Jury is 40% (vs 60% of the CCI Committee). The CCI Committee discusses the results and determines the approx. 15 ideas / start-ups that are admitted into the Acc. program

For both rounds the engagement of the target groups proceeded in a decentralised way, with each Spoke collecting ideas from students, researchers and early stage start-ups (third mission and others linked to universities) using a custom approach, and in synergy with the internal initiatives led by Technology Transfer and IP Valorisation Offices.

Engagement actions included: call for ideas, mini Spoke events, University newsletter, targeted SS actions, direct contacts with professors and researchers. The scouting system was improved after the 1st round and under guidance of the Program Leader and Scouting Officer. For the 2nd round a stronger focus was on targeted scouting efforts ("hunting"), addressing peculiar research groups. Guidelines to analyse patents and researchers' funded projects were developed and the engagement mechanisms were reinforced with desk analyses.

The selection process was composed of two decentralised evaluation steps - the pre-screening and the screening - conducted at Spoke level, followed by two centralised evaluation events - the Committee Evaluation and the Selection Day - moderated by the Program Leader and Manager.

Concerning common methodologies and tools, a template *Call for ideas* form with standard, simple fields for collecting the applications was developed and provided to the Scouting Specialists, who were free to implement it *as is* or use it in a customised way. All the applications were then reported in a centralised "pre-screening repository" for data analysis and reporting purposes.

A more structured form, the *Selection Form*, was developed and administered to those applicants that successfully passed the pre-screening step. This form was centralised and also required applicants to upload a pitch deck of their idea / project. Data collection tools and templates were gradually optimised and centralised (to ease post process data analysis) from round 1 to round 2.

Applicants were given access to **Educational materials** such as a selection of reviewed international benchmarks of entrepreneurial education.

In addition, custom training on the preparation of a Pitch Deck was finalised in a step-by-step [video guide](#) released by the Program Leader, Prof. Carlo Bagnoli.

Moreover, a standard [pitch deck template](#) was developed and provided to the applicants, guiding them in the presentation of their idea / project through the following key points:

CONTEXT

- Problem
- Solution
- Impact
- Market
- Competitors

STARTUP

- Governance
- Mission and Vision
- Business Strategy
- Business Model
- Financials

Apart from the pre-screening activity, which was an overall Yes/No assessment of the ideas / projects basic viability for the CCI Acceleration path, a [common set of evaluation criteria](#) was employed in all the selection steps.

The set included two [classification criteria](#) (Technology Readiness Level and Business Readiness Level) and 10 [selection criteria](#) that were developed for iNEST CCI with contributions by the CCI Committee. Five levels of scoring (see [Appendix A](#)) were established for each selection criterion with accurate descriptions of the meaning corresponding to each level.

The selection criteria were weighted as follows, adding up to a maximum final score of 100 points:

- 15% 1. Problem identification & relevance
- 15% 2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit
- 5% 3. Solution novelty
- 5% 4. Intellectual Property (IP) Protection
- 5% 5. Social and Environmental Impact
- 15% 6. Addressable market
- 5% 7. Market Competitiveness and Positioning
- 20% 8. Team Commitment and Execution Capability
- 5% 9. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
- 10% 10. Operating model scalability

The contribution of an [External Jury](#) was added to the evaluation procedure on the 2nd Selection Day (60% weight on final score for CCI Committee, 40% weight for External Jury). The overall Pre-Acceleration process is depicted in the following scheme:

It is important to note that a significant coordination effort was required to govern the process and the many-to-many interactions and interplays of decentralised and centralised stages.

In this regards, a key role was that of the Scouting Officer (SO), closely working with two assistants, who started with the initial engagement and training of the Scouting Specialists, requiring in the 1st round individual (almost weekly) coordination, then continued to involve all the Spokes periodically - as an increasingly united team, especially during the 2nd round - to discuss and review strategies, tools, activities, issues and results.

The SO and its team also served as a proactive connector and translator from SS/Spoke to CCI Committee and vice versa.

1.2. Description of the talent and ideas pool of applicants

The **target n.** of applications to the Open Call was 100+ for each round (min 10 per Spoke) while the actual number of collected applications and their progression towards the Acceleration program was:

Pre-Acc. funnel stage	Round 1	Round 2
Open Call	179	170
Selection Form submission	66	73
CCI Committee evaluation	40	41
Selection Day	32	30
Admission into Acceleration	16	16

The applications data was analysed with the aim of getting an overall picture of the pool of applicants, evidencing general trends and spotlighting peculiarities in each of the two rounds.

To build the dataset, the selected data source was the "Open Call" form (the first, simple form applicants had to fill in to enter the Pre-Acceleration process). For each round, even though a distinct Open Call was launched by each Spoke, the same form template was employed so that the 9 groups of answers constituted the largest possible database with corresponding fields.

Before starting the statistical analysis a data preparation step was conducted - independently - by the two Assistant Scouting Officers. The preparation consisted in classifying open-ended answers according to some predefined levels of factor variables such as: *Type of solution*; *Key Resources*; *Key Technology*; *Key Competencies*; *Qualifications*; *Innovation intensity*. The two independent classifications were then combined into a single version of the dataset of 349 observations.

The predefined levels of the principal factor variables were:

Key Resources (one or more options)	TecComp mix*	Key Technology	Innovation intensity	Type of solution
Patent	NNN	Hard	The solution is not innovative	Process
Non-patented technology	NNY	Soft	Incremental	Product
Personal competencies	NYN	Hard and Soft	Radical	Service
Brand	NYY	Bio and nanotech		Product-service
Material resources	YNN			System
Financial resources	YNY			Platform
No key resources	YYN			
	YYY			

**TecComp mix* is a composite variable which bundles information on the *Key Resources* of each application, specifically the mix of technology and competencies involved in the proposal: i.e. the three-letters sequence of Y (Yes) and N (No) corresponds to the presence / absence of: Patented technology, Non-patented technology, Personal competencies (in this order).

Origin institution	Applicant type	Key Competencies (1 or more options)	Macro theme / sector
1-UniBZ	Bachelor degree student / grad.	Technical-scientific	Smart Industries & Digital
2-UniTN	Master degree student / grad.	Economic-financial	Agrifood
3-UniUD	PhD candidate	Management	Health
4-IUAV	Research Grant Holder	Marketing and communication	Living & Energy
5-UniPD	Researcher (RTD-A, RTD-B, ...)	Administration	Cultural and Creative Industries
6-UniVE	Professor	Legal	Tourism
7-UniVR	Non academic / Freelance	Humanistic-social	Technologies and services for natural ecosystems
8-UniTS_PAA	Other	Artistic	
9-SISSA			

Team size	IP protection (only for round 2)	Previous entrepren. support paths (only for round 2)
1 - 2 members	No IP to protect	No
3 - 5 members	We don't know	Yes
> 5 members	IP that could be protected	
	Protected IP	

The only numeric variable was the applicant *Age*.

The same dataset was then used for inferential purposes, with a deeper analysis on the critical factors for accessing the Acceleration program (see [Section 2](#)).

In the following we describe and comment on the characteristics of the CC1 applicant pool through distributions and proportions in two fields of interest: **1. talents / people**, **2. ideas / projects**. Moreover, within each subsection, some comparisons were made between the full dataset (349 applications) and the subset of projects that were admitted into Acceleration (16 per round).

1.2.1. TALENTS / PEOPLE

The variables considered in this subsection are:

- Applicant type
- Origin Institution
- Age and Gender
- Team size
- Qualifications
- Competencies
- Previous startup experiences (round 2 data)

Applicant type

Overall, considering the two rounds together, *Bachelor* and *Master degree students/graduates* added up to almost 50% of the applicants, followed by 13% (each) of *PhDs* and *Non academic / Freelance* applicants, then by 8% of *Professors*.

Round 1 saw a very high engagement of *Bachelors* (36%), probably because of the “massive” use of the Open Call scouting approach by some of the Scouting Specialists (SS).

Conversely, in Round 2 there was an increase in the engagement of *PhDs* (from 8% in R1 to 18% in R2) and *Professors* (from 6% to 11%) that could be ascribed to an increased targeted scouting effort by the SS.

In addition, also the engagement of *Non academic* applicants was more substantial in R2, probably due to the greater diffusion and promotion of iNEST CCI opportunities also outside the academic environment.

The overall applicant type distribution (in R1+R2) was compared with the correspondent distribution within the subset of projects admitted to the Acceleration program.

Applicant type distribution per round and overall

To this end, for each applicant type, the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in the whole dataset (“overall” series) and in the Acceleration subset (“acc” series) was calculated. Percentual differences are reported in the following image (green arrows for positive values, red arrows for negative ones).

The Applicant types that display largely higher relative occurrence in the “acc” subset are those with high academic qualification (*R. grant holder, Researcher, Professor*), while *Non academic / Freelance* is the applicant type with the lowest “admission rate” for Acceleration (-52% occurrence), only followed by applications with *No data* for the applicant type (-100 %, none in the “acc” subset).

Applicant type % in r1+r2: dataset (overall) vs acceleration subset (acc)

Origin institution

The overall distribution of the applications by Origin Institution is the following: (in decreasing order) 24% UniVE, 24% UniTS_PAA, 12% UniUD, 9% UniVR, 8% UniPD, 7% UniTN, 6% IUAV, 5% UniBZ, 5% SISSA.

The contribution of the 9 Spoke leaders was almost the same in R1 and R2, except for Spoke 8- UniTS_PAA that was more active in engaging candidates in R1, and Spoke 6- UniVE that instead was more effective in R2.

The proportions can reflect differences in the prevalent scouting approach adopted by each SS, which we also assessed by looking at Applicant type per Origin Institution.

Applicant type per Origin institution

Expected values of each Applicant type per each Origin institution were calculated by means of simple proportions¹, assuming no relationships between the involved variables.

The delta between Observed value and Expected value of each cell was calculated and reported in a bubble chart (bubble size = delta, positive values in green, negative values in red).

Some trends were not consistent in the two rounds, whereas some others emerging in R1 were confirmed in R2. Such as the large positive deltas for the pairs: UniVE - Non academic / Freelance, IUAV - Bs, UniTS_PAA - Bs, SISSA - PhD, UniTN - PhD and Ms, UniVR - Professor, UniPD - Ms and Professor.

Applicant type per origin Institution in r2 (Obs value - Exp value)

Applicant age and gender

The CCI managed to attract candidates of diverse seniority, with applicant age ranging from 20 to 72, with a mean value of 35 years old. Concerning gender balance, the overall distribution was of about 65% M, 35% F.

The proportion was very similar in the two rounds but slightly variable throughout process stages. Interestingly, the highest overall % of female applicants is registered in the last stage (admission into the Acceleration program, 38% F).

No relevant patterns were observed when considering the distribution of applicant Gender by Applicant type.

¹ for example $ExpVal_{PhD,1-BZ} : ObsVal_{1-BZ} = ObsVal_{PhD} : ObsVal_{tot\ applications}$
 $\rightarrow ExpVal_{PhD,1-BZ} = ObsVal_{PhD} * ObsVal_{1-BZ} / ObsVal_{tot\ applications}$

Team size

In terms of team size, almost half (53%) of the ideas were proposed by individual applicants or duos, followed by 37% of teams with 3-5 members and a small number of larger teams (>5 members, 10%).

Team size distribution in dataset vs in acc. subset
% (counts)

	1-2	3-5	>5
r1_r2	▲ 53% (185)	▼ 37% (128)	▼ 10% (36)
r1_r2_acc	▼ 6% (2)	▲ 66% (21)	▲ 28% (9)

In this case the comparison with the “acc” subset reveals that very small teams were almost never admitted to the Acceleration phase (only 6% in acc. vs 53% in the whole dataset), while the occurrence of medium and large teams was higher in “acc” than in “overall”. The most frequent team size admitted to Acceleration was 3-5 members (66% in “acc”).

Qualifications

Team members' qualifications were considered in terms of relative presence, i.e. in the whole dataset versus in the Acceleration subset. For each Qualification the difference in percentual points was calculated as: $\Delta = \%_{acc} - \%_{overall}$. Deltas for R1+R2 data are reported in the following image (negative values in red, positive values in green).

The observed trend - which was consistent in the two rounds - could indicate that the “top 4” Qualifications a team should have to access

Acceleration are: *Professor, Researcher, PhD, Ms*. A reflection on the selection process and the intrinsic preference for highly academic teams is sparked by the fact that the “top 2” Qualifications are the highest in academic seniority and, at the same time, the “worst” performing Qualifications appear to be *Non academic / Freelance* and *Bs*.

Competencies

By analogy with Qualifications, team Competencies are displayed in terms of Δ presence between the Acceleration subset and the whole dataset (R1+R2) ($\Delta = \%_{acc} - \%_{overall}$). Again there was a consistent trend in R1 and R2, therefore the two rounds are considered jointly in the following image.

The “top 3” Competencies for Acceleration seem to be: *Technical-Scientific, Management, Administration*. The negative side, instead, is led by Competencies such as: *No data, Artistic and Humanistic-Social* Competencies.

This trend will be further investigated and discussed in the next Chapter, particularly in relation with other emerging trends in potentially connected variables (for example the ideas Macro theme).

Previous experience in startup creation and/or Acceleration

In the second round the “Open Call” form was integrated to assess previous startup experiences of the applicants. The closed question “Has any person of your team already participated (or is participating) in a startup creation and/or Acceleration process? (Yes / No)” was introduced.

The answer distribution is reported in the image, comparing the “overall” series and the “acc” series (R2 data).

For each of the possible answers the arrow indicates the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in the two series. It can be appreciated that the applications that display largely higher relative occurrence (+95%) in the acc. subset are those for which some team members already participated (or were participating) in a startup creation and/or Acceleration process (Yes). Moreover, of the 49 teams providing no answer to the question (*No data*) none got into the r2_acc subset (-100% occurrence).

1.2.2. IDEAS / PROJECTS

The variables included in this subsection are:

- Macro theme
- Type of solution
- Key Technology
- TecComp mix
- Innovation intensity
- Intellectual property (round 2 data)

Macro theme

The first characteristic of the ideas/projects that was assessed was the Macro theme (or sectoral orientation). In both rounds two of the 7 Macro themes were underrepresented, namely: *Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems* (5% overall) and *Smart Agri-food and Nutrition* (6% overall).

The remaining applications were quite evenly distributed among the other Macro themes, with leading options being: *Smart Industries* (23%) and *Creative industries* (21%) in R1+R2. Comparing the two rounds it can be noticed that R1 was characterised by a higher presence of proposals in *Health Tech and Services* (22%), while in R2 more projects in the *Creative Industries* (25%) considered applying to the iNEST CCI program.

Beyond proportions in the overall dataset, it is of particular interest to observe the Macro theme distribution in the Acceleration subset. The image below displays the comparison between the overall series and the “acc” series. For each of the Macro themes the arrow indicates the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in the two series.

Considering the two rounds together (R1+R2 data), two patterns stand out. The first is that only two Macro themes were found to be more present in the Acceleration subset than in the whole dataset: *Health Tech and Services* and *Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems*. The second one is the total absence of *Creative Industries* and *Tourism* ideas/projects in the Acceleration subset, meaning that projects in these sectors had an “admission rate” for Acceleration of -100%.

A slightly distinct behavior in R1 and R2 was found for projects in *Smart Agri-food and Nutrition* and *Smart Industries*, the former being part of the “good” themes for Acceleration in R1 (only with a +12% occurrence) but not in R2, the latter being in the “good” themes in R2 (+6% occurrence with respect to “overall” R2 series) but not in R1. Individual graphs of the subsets not reported here.

Macro theme per Origin institution

The Macro theme distribution by Origin institution was also investigated (image not reported) and one main pattern emerged as consistent in the two rounds: the observed values for *Creative Industries* and *Tourism* ideas / projects were particularly higher than the expected values² for UniVE and the observed values for *Health Tech and Services* were higher than the expected values for UniTN and UniVR.

In the case of UniVE and UniTN the prevalences could be related to a natural orientation of the two institutions - as Spoke Leaders - in harvesting ideas in line with their Spoke theme.

Type of solution

The ideas / projects were classified by Type of solution and their distribution was very similar in R1 and R2. Overall in R1+R2 the solution types occurrence (from highest to lowest) was: *Product* (26%), *Service* (22%), *Platform* (21%), *System* (13%), *Product-service* (10%), *Process* (8%). In R2 there were slightly more *Products* (28%) and *Platforms* (23%), but none of the types was predominant.

² Expected value calculation example $ExpVal_{Health_1-BZ} : ObsVal_{1-BZ} = ObsVal_{Health} : ObsVal_{tot} applications$

→ $ExpVal_{Health_1-BZ} = ObsVal_{Health} * ObsVal_{1-BZ} / ObsVal_{tot} applications$

Key technology

In both rounds about a quarter of the applicants proposed ideas / projects with *No key technology* (22% in R1, 27% in R2), and about 40% of the applications was based on *Soft technology*.

Looking at R1: within the tech-based applications, following those based on *Soft tech*, an equal amount (15%) was based on *Bio and nanotech* and *Hard+Soft* technology. Only 6% was based on *Hard* technology alone.

The distribution in R2 was similar to R1, but less projects entailed *Bio and Nanotech* and slightly more were based on *Hard* tech.

Key technology distribution per round and overall

TecComp mix

As introduced above in [Subsection 1.2](#) the “TecComp” mix is a variable that includes information on both technology and competencies present in each application. Thus the mix is a sequence of three letters (Y = Yes, N = No) corresponding to the presence / absence of: *Patented tech.*, *Non-patented tech.*, *Personal competencies* (in this order).

A very similar distribution is observed in the two rounds. Overall (in R1+R2) the TecComp mixes - in descending order of occurrence - were:

- NYN (39%)
- NYY (29%)
- NNN (19%)
- NNY (9%)
- YNY (3%)
- Other combinations (<2% each)

suggesting that, except for *NYY*, combinations with two *Y*s were rare (3% or less for each). On the other side of the spectrum, the most frequent combinations were *NYN* (only *Non-patented tech.*, 39%) and *NYY* (*Non-patented tech.* + *Personal Competencies*, 29%). Further observations were made by addressing the TecComp mix distribution by Macro Theme and in the Acceleration subset.

TecComp mix distribution per round and overall

TecComp mix in Acceleration subset and TecComp mix per Macro theme

In the left panel below, for each TecComp mix the arrow indicates the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in “overall” series and in “acc” series.

The TecComp mixes that display largely higher relative occurrences in the acc. subset are: YYY, YNY and NYY, hinting at the importance of having both personal competencies and tech assets in the team. TecComp mixes with overall lower relative occurrence in the “acc” subset are not displayed.

In the right panel the deltas between Observed value and Expected value of each cell were reported in a bubble chart (bubble size = delta, positive values in green, negative values in red). Expected values were calculated with proportions (assuming no relationships). TecComp mixes with all the deltas below +/- 10 are not reported.

TecComp mix % in r1+r2: dataset (overall) vs acc subset

TecComp mix per Macro theme (Obs value - Exp value)

It can be noticed that:

- NNN and NNY are particularly high in CCI but low in Health and Smart Industries
- NYN is particularly high in Smart Industries, while low in CCI
- NYY is quite high in Health and Smart Agrifood, but low in CCI and Tourism.

This pattern spurs considerations on sector specificities: *Smart Industries* seems to be a sector in which many projects have only *Non-patented technology* as Key Resource / asset; *Health* and *Smart Agrifood* instead emerge as sectors in which the combination of *Non-patented technology* and *Personal Competencies* is more frequent than expected; finally the *CCI* sector sees an excess of proposals without technological assets (and in some cases also without strong *Personal Competencies*).

Innovation intensity

The innovation intensity distribution was consistent in the two rounds: about 60% of the ideas / projects innovation intensity was *Incremental* and about 40% was *Not innovative*. Only a minority of the applications was considered to have the potential for *Radical* innovation (5% in R1, 2% in R2). Observing the percent occurrences in “overall” dataset compared to “acc” subset (image on the right), it can be appreciated that:

- the Innovation intensity that displays largely higher relative occurrence in the acc. subset is: *Radical* (+264%)
- a moderately higher presence in the acc. subset (+44%) is found for *Incremental* innovation
- *Not innovative* proposals have the lowest “admission rate” for Acceleration (-100% in R2, -82% in R1).

Innovation intensity %: dataset (overall) vs acc subset (acc)

For each Innovation intensity level in the graph the arrow indicates the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in the dataset (R1+R2) and in the “acc” series.

IP protection actions

Another integration of the “Open Call” form for round 2 was related to Intellectual Property protection. This was investigated by adding the closed question: “Have you completed or undertaken actions to protect the intellectual property (IP)?”. The distribution of the answers, including missing answers, from highest to lowest occurrence is the following:

- No, we have no IP that could be protected (28%)
- No, but we do have IP that could be protected (24%)
- No data (21%)
- We don't know (15%)
- Yes (12%)

The relatively high percentage of ideas / projects with IP that could be protected but still lacking protection actions (24%) induces a reflection on the role and effectiveness of the Technology Transfer and IP Valorisation Offices. In this sense, it is also not negligible that 15% of the applicants (in R2) have no clear ideas on their IP (*We don't know*).

Once again the answers distribution was compared with the Acceleration subset (image below). For each IP protection action the arrow indicates the percent difference between its occurrence (in %) in the R2 dataset and in the R2_acc subset.

The answers that display largely higher relative occurrence in the acc. subset are: *Yes* and *No, but we do have IP that could be protected*, hinting at the fact that - regardless of its protection status - IP had a certain relevance in determining admission to the Acceleration program. The other emerging pattern is that proposals with *No data* as answer to the IP protection question have the lowest “admission rate” for Acceleration (-100%). This suggests that incomplete fields in the applications could be a warning sign for exclusion from the selection process.

IP protection actions % in round2: dataset (r2) vs acceleration subset (r2_acc)

1.2.3. Peculiarities of each round

Both selection rounds of the Pre-Acceleration program followed the same structure, but revealed some differences in applicant profiles and project characteristics.

Round 1 had slightly more applications in total (179 vs 170) and showed a high engagement of Bachelor-level participants (36%), driven by broad scouting campaigns by some of the Scouting Specialists.

In contrast, in Round 2 the scouting team was able to attract more PhDs (18%) and Professors (11%), suggesting a more targeted and academically oriented scouting approach. Round 2 also saw greater involvement of Non-academic/freelance applicants, likely obtained by leveraging the SS professional networks to improve outreach beyond the academic sphere.

In terms of Origin Institution, the overall distribution remained relatively balanced across rounds, but Round 1 saw stronger participation from Spoke 8 (UniTS_PAA), while Spoke 6 (UniVE) was more active in Round 2. Some Origin institutions were less active in general but relatively more active towards specific Applicant types. This reflects differences in scouting strategies, with some Spoke leaders following their thematic focus while others focusing more on the types of applicants and teams.

On the people side, a consistent trend was observed across the rounds: higher academic qualifications and technical-scientific and management competencies had higher occurrences in the Acceleration subset compared to the overall dataset.

On the project side, the two rounds had similar distributions in terms of Type of solution and Innovation intensity, with most ideas being innovative in an incremental way.

Considering the Macro themes and sectoral orientation of the proposals, Round 1 featured more applications in *Health Tech and Services*, whereas Round 2 had an overrepresentation in *Creative Industries*.

Only Round 2 collected data on IP protection and previous startup experiences - two variables that displayed interesting patterns in relation to entering the Acceleration program: teams with past startup experience or IP-related awareness appear to have higher admission rates.

In both rounds, medium-sized teams (3-5 members) were more represented within the subset of ideas that accessed Acceleration. Finally, the TecComp mix (technology + competencies) patterns remained similar across rounds, with combinations including both assets being more rare but at the same time more successful in passing the selection stages.

While structurally aligned, Round 2 appears to have matured in quality, with more experienced applicants and improved data collection for deeper evaluation.

Taking the two rounds together, the iNEST CCI Pre-Acceleration program was effective in attracting a diverse pool of applicants, including *Bachelor* and *Master* students, *PhD candidates*, *Professors*, and notably, a growing share of *Non-academic / freelance* participants, especially in Round 2.

The presence of teams with *Non-patented technologies* and varied backgrounds - alongside the effort to engage actors outside the university ecosystem - indicates a deliberate and effective move beyond the typical top-down, research-to-market pathway led by Technology Transfer Offices.

Nonetheless, the selection outcomes showed that highly academic profiles were more represented among those admitted to Acceleration. This suggests that while the outreach was broad, the final filtering may have favored traditional indicators of academic tech-based excellence over more diverse or unconventional entrepreneurial profiles and less structured teams.

2. Critical factors for accessing the Acceleration program

This chapter investigates the key factors that influenced which applicants were selected to join the Acceleration phase of the iNEST CCI program. After [Chapter 1](#) offered a descriptive and comparative analysis of the projects and individuals who applied for the program, the aim here is to identify the drivers that guided access to the Acceleration phase. This second line of analysis is interpretative in nature and seeks to identify what characteristics distinguish the selected projects from those that were not admitted, given similar external conditions.

In other words, the core research question addressed in this chapter is: *What are the critical capabilities and resources (e.g., intellectual property, team expertise, proprietary technology, etc.) that distinguish startups that successfully transition from Pre-Acceleration to Acceleration?*

By focusing on the specific characteristics of admitted projects, we aim to retrospectively assess the selection process and uncover patterns that may reveal both its strengths and possible biases. This ex post evaluation can inform future improvements in selection procedures and contribute to a more robust and equitable design of entrepreneurial support initiatives.

The selection process adopted in iNEST CCI was not based on external benchmarks but was internally developed by the consortium, through a set of criteria shared among partners ([Appendix A](#)).

While this internal design ensured that the process reflected the collective goals and values of the partnership, it also implies that selection mechanisms may carry intentional or unintentional biases. This requires a degree of caution when interpreting statistical associations and predictive models.

However obvious, it is important to stress here that correlation does not imply causation. While we have taken steps to explore potential causal relationships, such as incorporating multivariate models to control for confounding factors, the limited sample size and the availability of only two rounds of data constrain our ability to draw definitive conclusions³.

Our analysis is based on a structured dataset containing information from both rounds of the iNEST CCI initiative, including variables derived from the application forms. We focus on a range of explanatory variables, including:

- Technological resources (e.g., patents, proprietary technologies);
- Human capital (e.g., academic vs. entrepreneurial background);
- Team composition and experience;
- Sector or field of application;
- Combinations of technical and personal resources (*TecComp mix*⁴).

To explore the relationship between these variables and the final selection outcome (Acceleration), we adopt a two-step statistical strategy:

1. **Bivariate association tests:** We run a series of one-to-one tests (Fisher's Test) to preliminarily identify which variables could be associated with selection. We included both categorical and binary predictors, covering technological assets (e.g. patents), human capital, team configuration, sectoral focus, etc.

³ Therefore, an observed statistical effect may reflect actual selection dynamics, but could also be influenced by specific biases of the selection process. These limitations call for prudence when interpreting our findings as representative of broader causal mechanisms.

⁴ *TecComp mix* is a composite variable which bundles information on the Key Resources of each application, specifically the mix of technology and competencies involved in the proposal: i.e. the three-letters sequence of Y (Yes) and N (No) corresponds to the presence / absence of: Patented technology, Non-patented technology, Personal competencies (in this order).

2. **Multivariate analysis:** We then estimate logistic regression models to assess the combined effect of different factors, while controlling for potential confounders and checking the robustness of our findings across rounds. Only variables found to be significant in both rounds via Fisher's test were included in multivariate logistic regressions.

This approach allowed us to explore whether combinations of factors maintained their predictive power when controlling for potential confounders. While the two rounds of the iNEST CC1 initiative represent a relatively limited empirical base, the coherence of certain results strengthens the interpretability of our findings.

Through this analytical approach, we aim to identify not only which individual factors are statistically significant, but also which combinations of factors are more likely to predict access to Acceleration. Particular attention is paid to whether certain variables (e.g., possession of IP, presence of mixed teams, or specific sectoral focus) emerge as consistently influential across both rounds.

The structure of the chapter is as follows:

- **Section 2.1** presents macro trends and highlights the main variables that exhibit a significant relationship with the Acceleration outcome.
- **Subsections 2.1.1, 2.1.2, and 2.1.3** provide a deeper dive into the three most relevant factors.
- **Section 2.2** offers reflections on the selection criteria, outcome patterns, and potential biases introduced by the selection design, suggesting areas for improvement and further monitoring.

By doing so, this chapter aims to provide both an evidence-based overview of the selection dynamics in iNEST CC1 and actionable insights for the refinement of future acceleration programs.

2.1. Macro trends

A limited set of factors consistently influenced the likelihood of admission to the iNEST CC1 Acceleration program. While the overall process involved heterogeneous projects and evolving methodologies across rounds, some variables emerged with stable and interpretable effects, offering meaningful insights into how selection dynamics developed.

The statistical results presented reflect the relationship between a variety of project- and team-level characteristics and the likelihood of being admitted to the Acceleration program. While not all associations are consistent across rounds, a number of patterns emerge with sufficient clarity to justify further investigation. Particular attention is paid to the coherence of effects between Round 1 and Round 2 and to the directionality of relationships, whether positive or negative.

The table below summarises the results of the bivariate association tests (**Fisher's Exact Test**) conducted separately for Round 1 and Round 2 of the iNEST CC1 initiative. Each row corresponds to a specific category within a broader explanatory factor (e.g., innovation intensity, team composition, resources), and the values in the last two columns indicate the observed effect on the *likelihood* of admission to the Acceleration phase.

The labels used in the *Round 1* and *Round 2* columns denote the direction and significance of the relationship:

- **Positive:** the category is positively and significantly associated with admission to the Acceleration program.
- **Negative:** the category is negatively and significantly associated with admission.
- **No effect:** the relationship is not statistically significant.

Table 2.1 summarizes the outcomes of the association tests across the two rounds. This offers a structured overview of the factors that appear to influence the likelihood of admission to the iNEST CC1 Acceleration program. Despite the complexity and diversity of the applicant pool, a relatively limited

subset of variables demonstrated statistically significant effects - either positive or negative - across the two selection rounds.

Table 2.1: Summary of Fisher's Test Results (Rounds 1 and 2)

FACTOR	CATEGORY	Round 1	Round 2
Innovation	The solution is not innovative	Negative	Negative
	Incremental	No effect	No effect
	Radical	Positive	Positive
Macro Theme	Smart Industries	Positive	Positive
	Smart Agri-food and Nutrition	No effect	No effect
	Health Tech and Services	Positive	Positive
	Smart and Sustainable Living	No effect	No effect
	Creative Industries	Negative	Negative
	Tourism	No effect	No effect
	Technologies and Services for Natural Ecosystems	No effect	Positive
Resources	Patent (patented technology)	No effect	Positive
	Non-patented technology	No effect	No effect
	Personal competencies	Positive	Positive
	Brand	No effect	No effect
	Material resources	No effect	Positive
	Financial resources	No effect	Positive
	No key resource	Negative	Negative
Tech & Competence Mix	YYY	No effect	Positive
	YYN	Negative	No effect
	YNY	No effect	Positive
	YNN	Negative	No effect
	NYY	Positive	Positive
	NYN	Negative	Negative
	NNY	No effect	No effect
	NNN	Negative	Negative
Key Technology	Hard	No effect	No effect
	Soft	No effect	Negative
	Hard and Soft	Positive	No effect
	Bio and nanotech	No effect	No effect
	No key technology	Negative	Negative
Solution Type	Process	No effect	No effect
	Product	No effect	Positive
	Service	No effect	Negative
	Product-service	No effect	No effect
	System	No effect	Positive
	Platform	No effect	No effect
Qualifications	Non academic/freelance	No effect	Negative
	Professor	Positive	Positive
	Researcher	Positive	Positive
	Research Grant Holder	No effect	No effect
	PhD	No effect	Positive
	Ms	Positive	No effect
	Bs	Negative	No effect
No data on qualification	No effect	No effect	
Competencies	Technical-scientific	Positive	Positive
	Economic-financial	No effect	No effect
	Managerial	Positive	Positive
	Marketing / Communication	No effect	No effect
	Administrative	Positive	Positive
	Legal	No effect	No effect
	Humanities / Social sciences	No effect	No effect
	Artistic	No effect	No effect
No data on competencies	Negative	No effect	
Team	1-2 members	Negative	Negative
	3-5 members	Positive	Positive
	>5 members	Positive	Positive

Among the positive drivers, three broad clusters emerge. First, *technological and intellectual property assets* appear to matter, albeit more clearly in the second round. While patent ownership did not show statistical relevance in Round 1, it became significant in Round 2, likely reflecting both an improved scouting framework and more accurate self-reporting by applicants. This shift suggests that formal IP was progressively internalised as a proxy for maturity and competitiveness in the selection process.

Second, *team composition* and *competence mix* stand out. Larger teams (3–5 and >5 members) were significantly more likely to be selected, consistently across both rounds. This effect aligns with the evaluation emphasis on execution capacity, and it may also indicate that teams with greater critical mass are more likely to structure their projects in a compelling and fundable way.

Furthermore, the TecComp configurations reinforce the value of complementarity: the NYY and YYY combinations - i.e., projects with technological components and strong personal competences - performed better, especially in Round 2. Conversely, projects lacking any structured resource (NNN) or composed solely of technical know-how without soft skills (NYN) were penalised.

Third, *sectoral orientation* appears to influence outcomes. Projects in Smart Industries and Health Tech were consistently favoured, likely due to their alignment with perceived market relevance, technological impact, and strategic fit with the iNEST CCI mission. By contrast, projects in the Creative Industries faced a significant disadvantage.

This may be attributed not only to a misalignment between the selection criteria - which favoured structured intellectual property, market scalability, and technical depth - and the more intangible, narrative-driven nature of creative ventures, but maybe also to a lower degree of familiarity among creative teams with the language and logic of the Pre-Acceleration application process.

The effect of *educational background* and *individual qualifications* offers further nuance. Professors and researchers were consistently associated with positive selection outcomes, suggesting a preference for institutional credibility or research-driven innovation. However, some qualifications (e.g., PhD and MSc) only reached significance in one round, suggesting potential variability in how academic signals were interpreted.

At the opposite end, projects involving bachelor's-level applicants (Bs) or those with missing competence data performed worse, raising questions about perceived readiness and the penalisation of incomplete profiles. Alternatively, this pattern may simply reflect the fact that such teams were not sufficiently prepared - due to lack of experience in the case of Bs - or not adequately motivated, as might be the case for those who failed to provide complete information.

Conversely, the *lack of key resources* emerges as a strong negative predictor, consistently penalizing projects with no tangible or intangible assets. Interestingly, *solution type* (e.g., product vs. service vs. system) did not heavily influence selection in both rounds, indicating that form factors may have been secondary to team and technological features.

Overall, the data reveal a selection mechanism that rewards structural preparedness, competence complementarity, and formalised innovation assets.

However, they also raise concerns about the potential exclusion of less codified or emerging forms of entrepreneurial value, such as those found in the cultural and creative sectors, or among smaller or less connected teams.

These patterns merit further attention in the interpretation of regression results and in future design revisions to ensure that evaluation frameworks do not unduly penalize diversity in entrepreneurial pathways.

Building on the results of the Fisher's Exact Tests, we proceeded to a **multivariate analysis** aimed at verifying whether the variables that emerged as significant in the bivariate setting retained their predictive power when considered jointly.

To ensure robustness and reduce the risk of overfitting, we limited the set of covariates included in the logistic regression models to those that had shown statistically significant associations with Acceleration admission in *both* Round 1 and Round 2⁵.

This criterion allowed us to isolate the most consistently influential factors across selection cycles and to test their combined effect while controlling for potential interactions and confounders.

The transition to a multivariate framework thus provides a more stringent test of the explanatory power of each variable, offering a deeper understanding of which characteristics most strongly predict successful access to the Acceleration program.

Table 2.2: Summary of Logistic Regression Results (Rounds 1 and 2)

FACTOR	CATEGORY	Round 1	Round 2
Innovation	The solution is not innovative	Negative	No effect
	Radical	Positive	Negative
Macro Theme	Smart Industries	Positive	Positive
	Health Tech and Services	Positive	Positive
	Creative Industries	Negative	Negative
Resources	Personal competencies	No effect	No effect
	No key resource	Negative	Negative
Key Technology	Hard and Soft	Positive	No effect
	No key technology	Negative	Negative
Qualifications	Professor	No effect	No effect
	Researcher	No effect	Positive
Competencies	Technical-scientific	Positive	Positive
	Managerial	No effect	No effect
	Administrative	No effect	No effect
Team	1-2 members	Negative	Negative
	3-5 members	Positive	Positive
	>5 members	Positive	No effect

The **logistic regression** analysis reinforces and refines some of the insights emerging from the bivariate tests, while also offering a more robust view of the most stable predictors of admission to the Acceleration phase.

By focusing only on the variables that displayed significance in both rounds under Fisher's test, the model isolates those features that hold explanatory power beyond simple pairwise associations, accounting for joint effects and potential collinearity.

Sectoral orientation confirms its relevance: *Smart Industries* and *Health Tech & Services* maintain a strong positive association with selection, underscoring the strategic alignment between these domains and the iNEST CCI objectives.

These sectors likely embody a combination of technological maturity, perceived market potential, and institutional interest, making them particularly compelling to the selection committee.

Conversely, *Creative Industries* projects remain negatively associated with admission, a result that is not only consistent with the previous bivariate analysis but may also reflect a structural misalignment on two fronts.

On the one hand, these projects may fit less easily within an evaluation framework that prioritizes technological assets, market readiness, and scalability. Their value often lies in exploratory, early-stage

⁵ Therefore, the dependent variable is binary, indicating whether a project was admitted to the Acceleration phase (1) or not (0). Independent variables were selected conservatively: we included only those factors that had shown a statistically significant association with admission in both rounds of Fisher's Exact Test. This approach balances explanatory rigor with parsimony, helping reduce model overfitting and enhancing the interpretability of results across a relatively limited dataset.

knowledge creation rather than in immediately exploitable technologies, which can make their assessment more challenging when judged through standard innovation or venture-building criteria.

On the other hand, they may also lack certain characteristics - such as replicability, protection mechanisms (e.g., IP), or capital-intensive development trajectories - that evaluators often perceive as prerequisites for success in Acceleration. As a result, evaluators tend to find some categories of projects more attractive (typically life-science or deep-tech initiatives), particularly when the program emphasizes entrepreneurship education.

This dual limitation suggests that, unless specific criteria are adopted, certain domains (e.g. in the digital apps or digital transformation) may systematically underperform regardless of project quality, raising important questions about inclusivity and sectoral diversity in early-stage innovation support programs.

Team configuration once again emerges as a critical factor. *Small teams (1-2 members)* show a statistically significant negative effect, while *medium-sized teams (3-5 members)* are positively associated with admission in both rounds. *Larger teams (>5)* only show a positive effect in Round 1, suggesting a possible diminishing return or greater heterogeneity in Round 2 teams. The consistent advantage for teams with 3-5 members may reflect an optimal trade-off between agility and capability in early-stage ventures.

In terms of technological resources, the presence of *no key technology* remains a strong negative predictor, reinforcing the idea that projects lacking identifiable technological components may face a disadvantage. Interestingly, the previously observed positive effect of *combined hard and soft technologies* (in Round 1) does not hold in the multivariate setting, pointing to a more nuanced interpretation: technological sophistication alone may not be enough without complementary assets or execution readiness.

Among the individual-level variables, only *technical-scientific competencies* retain a stable and significant effect. This suggests that, even when controlling for sector and team variables, projects anchored in scientific expertise are systematically favored. Other qualifications (e.g., professors, researchers) lose significance in the multivariate context, indicating that institutional affiliation per se is less predictive than the content and configuration of the project.

Taken together, the regression results confirm a selection logic that favors structured, technically grounded projects with a balanced team composition and clear sectoral fit.

While these criteria align with the goals of structured acceleration, they may also risk narrowing the pipeline by penalizing projects that are exploratory, creative, or unconventional in form. This underlines the importance of continually refining evaluation frameworks to ensure they can capture value across a broader spectrum of entrepreneurial trajectories.

2.1.1. Degree of innovation

The degree of innovation expressed in each project emerged as a critical determinant in the selection process for the iNEST CCI Acceleration program. Both Fisher's exact tests and subsequent logistic regression analysis highlighted this factor as statistically significant, underlining its weight in shaping evaluators' decisions and justifying a deeper investigation.

Projects were evaluated on a three-level innovation scale: "not innovative," "incremental innovation," and "radical innovation." Proposals categorised as "not innovative" - those lacking any meaningful novelty, whether technological, methodological, or conceptual - were consistently associated with negative selection outcomes across both rounds, indicating a structural misalignment with the program's strategic goals.

Conversely, the statistical treatment of “incremental” innovations revealed no significant relationship with the probability of being selected. These projects neither increased nor decreased the likelihood of entering the Acceleration phase, suggesting a form of neutrality in the eyes of evaluators: their limited transformative scope may not have penalised them, but it also failed to serve as a distinctive advantage.

More nuanced dynamics emerged with respect to “radical” innovations. Fisher’s tests gave a clear result across the dataset: radical innovation was significantly associated with a higher probability of selection. However, the results from the logistic regression analysis revealed round-specific divergences. In Round 1, radically innovative projects were positively associated with Acceleration outcomes, indicating an early-stage preference for bold, high-impact ideas. In Round 2, however, the relationship turned negative, with radical innovation correlating with a lower likelihood of selection.

This reversal may reflect an evolving focus within the selection process. As the program matured, evaluators may have shifted their emphasis toward feasibility, market readiness, and implementation capacity. While radical innovation can be compelling in its disruptive potential, it may also carry heightened execution risk or lack immediate scalability - factors that could have weighed more heavily in Round 2 assessments. This shift is also consistent with the performance expectations typically associated with acceleration programs, which - even if not made explicit - tend to revolve around indicators such as the quality and viability of ventures generated, the advancement in Venture Maturity Index (or similar IRL-based proxies), measurable progression metrics (e.g., funding raised or maturity improvements), and broader regional, academic, or technology-transfer impacts. Projects perceived as more immediately capable of contributing to these metrics are therefore likely to have been viewed more favorably in the later stages of the process.

Moreover, when analysed alongside other variables in the logistic regression, the beneficial effect of radical innovation appears to diminish. This suggests that radical proposals - despite their conceptual appeal - may have systematically underperformed in other key dimensions such as team composition, alignment with priority sectors, or the presence of enabling resources. Although not explicit in the selection criteria, triggers to not pursue and favourably evaluate some radical innovation projects might have been the need of a longer bootstrap effort from founders or the high capital injection requirements to sustain such ventures.

As a result, their overall evaluation may have suffered, highlighting the need for a balanced profile that integrates visionary content with organisational, strategic robustness and return on investment, either in public or in private entity domains.

That said, it is important to acknowledge a key limitation: the number of observations classified as “radical” innovation was very small - only 9 in Round 1 and just 3 in Round 2. Therefore, while the considerations above remain valid, they should not be overgeneralised, as the patterns observed may reflect case-specific or isolated circumstances.

Anecdotal evidence suggests that, in many innovation programmes, projects with clearer market potential or an easier path to funding tend to be viewed more favourably than ideas that are highly visionary but harder to implement. Innovation acts as a basic filter, necessary to distinguish promising applications, but insufficient on its own to guarantee selection, as proposals that show practical next steps beyond innovativeness usually have an advantage. In iNEST, this pattern appeared only to some extent. While projects with more obvious development routes were often easier to advance, some visionary proposals were still considered promising when they aligned well with the programme’s goals and offered a credible long-term direction, even in the absence of immediate marketability.

These findings suggest that applicants should not only demonstrate innovative value but also situate it within a credible roadmap aligned with the iNEST CC1 program’s evolving evaluation logic.

2.1.2. Team size

Among all the variables tested in the selection analysis of iNEST CC1, team size emerged as one of the most stable and influential predictors of admission to the Acceleration program. Both bivariate and multivariate analyses consistently show that projects involving only 1-2 members were significantly less likely to be selected, while those with 3-5 members were positively associated with admission in both rounds. Larger teams (with more than five members) also showed a positive effect, though this was more evident in Round 1 and less so in Round 2 (when considered simultaneously with other factors).

The coherence of this result across rounds - and its statistical robustness in the logistic regression - suggests that evaluators systematically favored teams reaching a certain “critical mass”. This tendency likely reflects both cognitive and organisational logics. From a cognitive standpoint, teams with multiple members may be perceived as more capable of covering the diverse skill sets needed to turn an idea into a viable business. Please note that possible governance blocks due to mis-designed cap tables (poor clawback, incorrect equity split, bad leavers clauses) leading to decision making paralysis are beyond this report scope.

In a program that explicitly values execution capability and scalability, this complementarity may serve as a proxy for operational readiness. On the organisational side, larger teams may inspire more confidence in terms of commitment and continuity, provided that the “shareholders' agreements” and the “statute” terms allow an effective decision making among the larger team.

A single founder or duo may raise concerns about availability, risk of abandonment, or bottlenecks in decision-making. In contrast, a team of three to five members may distribute tasks more efficiently and demonstrate early forms of internal organisation - two traits likely to be rewarded in structured acceleration settings.

Moreover, although larger teams may *suggest* the presence of early coordination mechanisms, this relationship is not automatic. Competences, decision-making synchronisation, and organisational readiness are normally evaluated during due-diligence processes rather than inferred from team size alone. These latent organisational dynamics often become explicit during the Pre-Acceleration phase. In this context, having more members increases the likelihood that critical business elements are more clearly articulated and better documented. This, in turn, increases the chances of being admitted to Acceleration.

Additionally, the presence of a larger team inherently entails that the initial idea has undergone more rounds of informal scrutiny. It is more likely that a multi-member team has debated and validated their concept internally, subjecting it to multiple perspectives and refinements before submitting it for external evaluation.

In this sense, the project is already somewhat “pre-validated” through internal dialogue, increasing its coherence and credibility in the eyes of the selection committee.

The interviews with members of the selection committee support this interpretation. Several evaluators noted that teams with more than two members were better able to articulate their strategy, distribute speaking roles during pitches, and respond to questions with domain-specific confidence. This suggests that team size is not only a statistical proxy, but also a visible signal of credibility during selection events. Whether that is correlated to the census size or to a multi competence contribution inherent to a larger team size, is to be determined.

However, this emphasis on “critical mass” may also carry unintended consequences. It risks penalizing single founders or highly innovative duos who, while not lacking in competence or motivation, may fall outside the expected team composition.

Furthermore, it may discourage early applications from individuals still in the ideation stage, who might benefit from acceleration precisely to build a team.

To mitigate this risk, future editions of the program might consider explicitly supporting smaller teams in the Pre-Acceleration phase - offering team-matching services, mentorship on team building, or even allowing for “conditional” admission based on subsequent team expansion. Such adjustments could preserve the benefits of team robustness while keeping the pipeline open to promising but understructured initiatives.

2.1.3. Sectoral orientation

Among the explanatory variables examined in the selection process of iNEST CCI, sectoral orientation emerged as one of the most decisive and consistent predictors of admission to the Acceleration phase.

This result holds across both statistical approaches: the bivariate association tests and the multivariate logistic regression. In particular, three macro sectors stand out for their stable influence - two positively and one negatively - on the likelihood of being selected: *Smart Industries*, *Health Tech and Services*, and *Creative Industries*.

Projects classified under *Smart Industries* were positively and significantly associated with admission to Acceleration in both rounds. This trend remained robust in the regression models, confirming that sectoral alignment with perceived technological maturity and market relevance played a critical role in selection decisions.

Smart Industries projects often combine engineering depth, potential for industrial application, and tangible technological assets - all features that relate well with the selection criteria adopted by the iNEST CCI Committee. These projects are likely to be easy to evaluate, compatible with funding logics, and close to what is expected from innovative projects.

Similarly, *Health Tech and Services* projects showed a strong and consistent positive effect across all analyses. These projects likely benefitted from the dual narrative of social impact and technological innovation, often leveraging academic or clinical research outputs.

Moreover, the post-pandemic context likely reinforced the perceived relevance of health-related innovation, increasing the evaluators' sensitivity to these themes. Several health tech proposals also included digital health solutions, medical devices, or diagnostic tools - domains where regulatory awareness and clinical validation pathways signaled maturity and credibility.

Notably, even when such projects were still at an early stage, their thematic relevance and alignment with regional and national innovation priorities may have tilted the selection process in their favor.

By contrast, projects in the *Creative Industries* domain faced a consistent and statistically significant disadvantage. Both rounds showed a negative association with admission, and this pattern held in the regression analysis. This outcome points to a potential structural misfit between the characteristics of creative projects and the implicit expectations of the selection framework.

Creative industries often rely on intangible assets, narrative-driven value creation, and non-linear development paths that may not align with criteria such as IP rights valorisation, market scalability, and technological readiness.

Moreover, they frequently draw on the unique, non-replicable talent of their promoters - an asset that, while essential to the project's value proposition, may be difficult to assess or compare using standardised criteria.

As a result, these projects - while potentially rich in cultural and social value - may have struggled to meet the formal indicators used in the selection grid. This raises concerns about inclusivity and the risk of systematically underrepresenting sectors that do not conform to tech-centric evaluation logics.

Overall, the importance of sectoral orientation in predicting access to Acceleration reflects both strategic alignment and possible evaluative biases. On the one hand, it is reasonable - and even desirable - for acceleration programs to prioritise sectors that are better positioned to address the program's intended challenges and stakeholders' expectations, whether these relate to regional development goals, technological advancement, or the ability to generate investable ventures. In many cases, however, the sectors with the highest private funding potential are not necessarily those with the most transformative missions: digital or app-based initiatives can often monetise quickly by leveraging mature cloud and platform infrastructures, yet they may fall short of the "change-the-world" aspiration associated with sustainability, life-science, or deep-tech projects. This tension between fundability and transformative ambition may therefore shape evaluators' behaviour in ways that are not always fully explicit.

On the other, the observed patterns suggest a need for balance: if the same sectors are consistently favored, the program risks narrowing the scope of supported innovation and excluding valuable but market-pull driven ideas versus tech-push ones. Future iterations could consider defining sector-specific selection paths or complementary support instruments for fields like the creative economy, where innovation takes forms not easily captured by standard metrics.

2.2. Considerations on selection criteria, selection outcomes and potential biases

The findings presented in this chapter provide a valuable opportunity to reflect on the selection dynamics of the iNEST CCI Acceleration program - not merely as an ex post evaluation, but as a basis for informing and improving future similar initiatives.

While the observed patterns demonstrate a reasonable degree of internal coherence and alignment with the program's objectives, they also raise important questions about the implicit priorities embedded in the selection process and the potential for structural biases.

One important consideration is the possibility that the criteria adopted by the evaluation committee - explicit or otherwise - have contributed to shaping the cohort of applicants. In other words, beyond influencing which projects were selected, even if the criteria were not known to participants, it was encouraged the candidacy of initiatives that perceived themselves as aligned with the dominant narrative of innovation promoted by iNEST, and implicitly discouraging less conventional or non-technological proposals. This selection driving force, while understandable in competitive funding environments, may lead to a narrowing of the innovation spectrum supported by the program.

Indeed, one of the clearest patterns emerging from the data is that project configurations characterised by technical robustness, mid-sized teams, and alignment with high-priority sectors have consistently benefitted from the evaluation framework. These findings suggest that the selection process implicitly rewards structural maturity, sectoral congruence and ideological appeal of the proposals.

While such criteria are logical within an academic acceleration context - where impact-to-be, time, resources are paramount - they may also contribute to the systematic exclusion of alternative or less ambitious forms of innovation closer to solution proposals whose impact pertains to the pure *emotional* category (non-technology/IP driven). This is especially relevant when considering the case of projects from the *Creative Industries*, solo or duo teams, and ventures lacking clear technological innovation assets, whilst leveraging established technology stack infrastructure.

These projects may underperform when judged against standard metrics such as IP, social or economic impact, team size. However, they may nonetheless represent meaningful sources of cultural, social, or even commercial innovation. Their underrepresentation may point to a narrow meaning of "innovation" - one that favours engineering over expression, standardisation over originality, and organisational solidity over emergent potential.

Another element that deserves attention is the evolving evaluative logic between rounds. The case of radical innovation, for instance, highlights how initial enthusiasm for transformative ideas may be tempered over time by pragmatic concerns about feasibility and risk. Ensuring greater transparency and stability in evaluative criteria across rounds could enhance trust and improve applicant alignment.

Importantly, the choice to limit the logistic regression to factors significant in both rounds, while statistically reasonable, may also have hidden context-specific insights.

Future iterations might benefit from a more nuanced model that distinguishes between structural and contingent predictors of success. This would require expanding the scope and quality of data collection - not only in terms of quantitative descriptors, but also through richer qualitative inputs that could enhance the deepness of analysis and help surface latent patterns not captured by running categorical variables.

For example, current datasets do not systematically capture factors such as the internal cohesion, motivation and decision-making of the founding team, the perceived clarity and ambition of the project's long-term vision, the maturity of strategic partnerships, or previous entrepreneurial experiences beyond formal track records. These elements, while difficult to code *ex ante*, may significantly influence a project's potential for acceleration and would benefit from structured qualitative observation or post-evaluation feedback loops.

Lastly, a reflection is warranted on the potential trade-offs between inclusivity and efficiency. As the iNEST CCI program continues to evolve, there may be value in designing differentiated pathways for different innovation archetypes.

Tailored support tracks - e.g., one for deep-tech ventures, another for cultural or social innovation - could preserve the program's performance orientation while opening up space for more diverse expressions of entrepreneurial potential.

At the same time, clearer communication of selection criteria and expected project profiles could help reduce mismatches in applicant expectations and increase perceived fairness.

More broadly, while the iNEST CCI selection framework has proven effective in selecting projects with strong structural features and sectoral alignment, it also appears to filter out less conventional expressions of entrepreneurial potential.

To mitigate this, future iterations could benefit from more adaptive evaluative criteria, possibly including narrative components, founder motivations, or contextual relevance - especially for projects emerging from underserved territories or atypical innovation environments.

Furthermore, complementary non-competitive instruments (such as preparatory labs or bootcamps) could be introduced to engage promising teams not yet ready for full acceleration. These adjustments would allow the program to simultaneously maintain high standards and broaden its reach, thus better fulfilling its systemic innovation mandate.

These reflections on the front-end of the Acceleration process find a natural complement in the next chapter, which shifts the focus to the post-selection phase.

By exploring concrete indicators of startup performance and success following participation in the program, [Chapter 3](#) aims to assess whether the implicit selection preferences observed in this analysis are also predictive of tangible outcomes, and to what extent the program is achieving its long-term innovation and impact objectives.

3. Success factors during and after the Acceleration program

After analysing CCI activities and drivers related to admission into the Acceleration phase, we aim to assess the effectiveness of the Acceleration phase by identifying the success factors during and after the program.

Therefore, this chapter addresses a fundamental research question within the iNEST CCI initiative: *What are the most tangible results achieved by the accelerated teams and which teams were most successful? In which areas of development the support offered by the CCI program needs to be revised and improved?*

So, now the focus is not on determinants, it is on outcomes: what happened after admission, and which variables best explain the variance in performance among the accelerated projects.

To answer this, we develop a comparative analysis between teams with different performance levels, based on a set of success metrics. Given the heterogeneity of projects and backgrounds, a multidimensional approach was adopted, combining organisational, technological, network-related, and economic indicators.

A caveat of this type of analysis is that Round 1 has concluded for over a year, allowing for a post-program observation window, while Round 2 officially ended on June 26, 2025, limiting the possibility of post-program evaluation.

Therefore, this chapter mainly analyses success patterns emerging from Round 1 and formulates hypotheses to be verified ex post on Round 2 data, in a learning and cross-validation perspective.

Hence, we aim to provide insights into what *really works* in early-stage research entrepreneurship, offering evidence-based guidance for the future evolution of CCI and other Acceleration frameworks within the iNEST ecosystem.

3.1. The Acceleration program: structure, contents and implementation

First, it is important to understand how the Acceleration program was designed and implemented across Round 1 and Round 2. This includes the educational model, coaching system, evaluation criteria, and support tools employed to strengthen the entrepreneurial capabilities of the selected teams.

An Acceleration Framework was developed for the 1st round and with a learning-by-doing approach optimised for the 2nd round: a standardised “educational model” is provided through a centralised program based on itinerant workshops.

The marked difference in maturity of the 15 start-ups that entered the course made it difficult to adapt the content and delivery methods to everyone's needs. For Round 2, an attempt was made to overcome this heterogeneity of initial BRLs with more support by the SS during Pre-Acceleration and by the coaches during Acceleration.

The 2nd round Acceleration framework, also based on the collected feedback, was characterised by a higher number of workshops (from 6 to 8) with reduced theory content (only 45 min lectures per work session) and more practical work with the coaches for building a solid strategic document (“strategic plan”) at the basis of the pitch⁶.

The resulting program pillars are therefore:

- the intensive work for the creation of a strategic plan (“backbone” and common thread of all the workshops);
- the robust coaching structure (for each team: 1 operative/junior coach + 1 expert/senior coach);
- the continuous in-presence participation;
- the workshop modalities (high hands-on approach).

⁶ Indeed, the system adopted in the first round demonstrated limitations in supporting the teams, primarily because of the absence of precise tasks to be carried out between workshops and insufficient time (in class) to work with the coaches. Some workshops saw the theoretical lesson consume up to two of the four hours, and in the remaining time each coach had to assist 2-3 teams (meaning individualised support was not extensive).

Pillars for the Accelerator (2nd round)

Key elements based on feedback and experience from the 1st Acceleration round

Such methodological curvature of the Acceleration framework was functional in giving more structure to the start-ups, equally enhancing the communication part (pitch) with the documentation part for each of the elements underlying a business plan / strategic plan, starting with the development from POC to MVP.

In addition to the in-presence workshops and the remote coaching support (with weekly online meetings), in the 1st round a cycle of 5 webinars was also offered (Presentation of psychological types; Marketing, customer acquisition, sales; IP strategy; Data protection; Legal issues - Shareholders' agreements, term sheets, investment agreements) but revealed low interest and impact.

In the 2nd round, instead, the offer included two services on request: the first for patent and intellectual property advice, the second for legal support (term sheet review, advice on incorporation of innovative start-ups).

The contents of the workshops are reported in the following scheme (for round 2) and in the summary table for both rounds with indication of the workshop location:

Workshops

Acceleration workshops summary table:

ROUND 1			ROUND 2		
Location	WS#	Workshop title	Location	WS#	Workshop title
UNITS	1	Governance, Mission, Vision, Strategy and Business Model	UNITN	1	Introduction and presentation of the strategic plan
		Problem and potential customer			
UNIPD	2	Solution, value proposition and product POC	UNIVR	2	Problem, actual solution and proposal
		Market, competitors and potential competitive positioning			
UniTN - Sol	3	Pitch session test	UNIUD	3	Market and competition
		Profit Model			
SISSA	4	Operational model	UNIVE	4	Governance, mission & vision, strategy, business model; tools for AI
		Economic-financial model			
IUAV	5	Fundraising	IUAV	5	Pitch clinic #1 (cut-off)
		Company constitution and corporate governance			
UNIVR	6	Pitch clinic	UNIBZ	6	Action plan & Eco-Fin Plan
UNIVR	-	Demo Day	UNITS	7	Eco-Fin Plan & funding
			UNIVR	8	Pitch clinic #2 (cut-off)
			UNIVE	-	Demo Day

Concerning the coaching system, the model was reinforced for the 2nd round, assigning to each start-up 1 “expert/senior coach” bringing vertical expertise and 1 “operative coach” offering weekly 1h-meetings to better assist the co-founders throughout all the program. Based on competencies and commitment, some of the Scouting Specialists were also involved in the “operative coach” role.

Attentive progress tracking and prompt corrective measures were ensured by the Acceleration management team (consolidated with the lead of UniTN/HiT and UniVR, supported by the Scouting Officer, Assistant Scouting Officers and Communication team) who met with weekly frequency. Coach coordination meetings were also regularly held (bi-weekly) to collect coaches feedback on the teams activities and commitment.

Satisfaction surveys were periodically administered to the participant teams to assess and adapt the Acceleration program structure and features. A specific software for the management of acceleration programs, called *AcceleratorApp*, was introduced in round 2 to support more efficient work tracking, knowledge sharing, pace-keeping and reporting. This web-based platform served as a central spot and repository for all activities related to the Acceleration phase.

Looking at the implementation of the Acceleration phase: the 1st round of the program was offered to 16 start-ups and completed by 11 of them. Towards the end of the 1st Acceleration program, some of the startups received a spontaneous interest from a number of different investors (such as: industrial, corporate and institutional funds and ventures, incubators, and even private equities). Therefore, 6 start-ups were guided by an Acceleration task force in the development of key documents to strengthen their preparedness for dialoguing with investors.

The 2nd round of the program is ongoing and is being offered to 15 start-ups; for this cycle two intermediate cut offs were introduced to filter out of the program those teams that do not demonstrate

sufficient commitment and that are not ready to complete the work required for a good performance at the Demo Day.

In preparation for the cut-offs, the coaches assess their assigned start-ups using a common set of criteria, taking into account the work done by the team and the progress of the “strategic plan”.

The cut-offs consist of a pitch session in which each start-up has 5 minutes of pitch and 5 minutes of Q&A by an external jury, whose members give their personal assessment (using a simplified set of criteria, and also consulting the strategic plans developed by the start-ups). The coach average score and the external jury average score, per team, are then weighted with a 60 % : 40 % ratio.

The internal set of evaluation criteria was derived from the selection criteria used in Pre-Acceleration by slightly reviewing the relative weights and adding the criterion n. 11 related to the Go to market / Action plan. The resulting set is the following:

- 15% 1. Problem identification & relevance
- 15% 2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit
- 5% 3. Solution novelty
- 5% 4. Intellectual Property (IP) Protection
- 5% 5. Social and Environmental Impact
- 10% 6. Addressable market
- 5% 7. Market Competitiveness and Positioning
- 15% 8. Team Commitment and Execution Capability
- 5% 9. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
- 10% 10. Operating model scalability
- 10% 11. Go to market / Action plan

The simplified set of criteria used by the external jury was the following:

- 30% 1. Investability
- 20% 2. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity
- 30% 3. Team Commitment and potential Execution Capability
- 20% 4. Gut feeling.

In both cases each criterion was defined on a five levels scale, adding up to a maximum final score of 100 points.

3.2. Definition of “success” metrics

The ultimate goal of the CCI transversal activity was to support the transformation of early-stage projects into solid, market-ready start-ups.

This section examines whether that goal was effectively achieved by analysing the actual progress made by the accelerated teams, particularly those from Round 1, which concluded over a year ago and thus allow for a more robust post-program evaluation.

The analysis is based on a set of shared success metrics designed to capture key dimensions of start-up development, including organisational consolidation, technological and business readiness, ecosystem integration, and financial outcomes.

The aim of these metrics is twofold: evaluating the overall effectiveness of the CCI initiative in fostering entrepreneurial growth, and testing whether the critical factors for accessing Acceleration identified in Chapter 2 are also predictive of tangible success during and after the program.

To ensure coherence with the structure of the Acceleration path, the metrics were developed in alignment with the final workshop topics, where each team outlined a detailed roadmap from *Proof of Concept* (POC) to *Minimum Viable Product* (MVP) through an analytical Action Plan.

This plan defined specific goals and priority actions in areas such as product development, customer acquisition, and ecosystem engagement, dimensions that are now at the core of our evaluation.

The metrics were grouped into four areas: AREA 1: Team, AREA 2: Technology and Business Readiness progression, AREA 3: Network / Ecosystem, AREA 4: Economic-financial aspects, and each success metric was translated into a question to collect data from the participants.

A questionnaire was administered to the accelerated teams, asking to share information considering two distinct periods: from Selection Day to Demo Day and from the Demo Day on (+7 months), thus including their latest developments in the latter period.

The questionnaire was distributed in June 2025 to the start-ups from Round 1. For Round 2, the survey will be administered at a later stage, some months after the conclusion of their Acceleration journey. The specific metrics were:

Area	Metrics	ID
Organisational success	Formalisation of the legal entity (incorporation, registration of VAT number, ...)	M01
	Team retention	M02
	Team growth	M03
Operational success	Technological / prototype advancement (TRL from ... to ...)	M04
	Product testing and certification	M05
	IP protection / valorisation	M06
	Developments in market approach	M07
	Developments in market access	M08
Systemic / network success	Subsequent involvement in other pathways (e.g. incubators, accelerators)	M09
	Recognitions obtained	M10
	Partnerships set up with universities or companies in the area	M11
	Expressions of interest from investors	M12
Economic / financial success	Revenues generated	M13
	Funds raised	M14
	Banks financing	M15

A final open-ended question was added to ask the teams which are the main changes they perceived since the beginning of the Acceleration process and favoured by having participated in it.

The results of the questionnaire are currently being collected. While the present section focuses on the design and intended analytical function of the success metrics, the actual evaluation will be conducted once the full set of responses is available.

The structure of the metrics itself is already an asset for future monitoring, enabling a consistent and comparative assessment across cohorts.

The forthcoming analysis will contribute to the broader learning effort of the iNEST CCI initiative, helping to validate or refine assumptions drawn from earlier phases and providing evidence-based insights for the continuous improvement of future acceleration programs.

3.3. Qualitative insights from Round 1 and hypotheses formulation

The first cycle of data collection allows us to observe how Round-1 founders perceive their own advancement along the Acceleration path. Although these results stem from self-assessment rather than objective measurement, they represent the earliest empirical indications of where progress appears most concrete and which types of teams are currently able to benefit the most from the CCI support model. The questionnaire results point to four distinct evolution patterns, each conditioned by the initial maturity, internal cohesion, and sectoral context of the teams.

Here we report observations on the **four areas of development** addressed by the 15 metrics, namely: Organisation, Validation (operational success), Network, Economic-financial aspects.

- 1) **Organisation readiness** is the area in which improvements were perceived most strongly, but also most unevenly across cases. Teams already incorporated at programme entry tend to describe a period of internal consolidation, with clearer role allocation and, in several cases, the expansion of the group to attract key capabilities. Among less mature initiatives, the most recurring pattern is the shift from concept to formal structure, with founders working on legal set-up, documentation, governance, and - crucially - on aligning personal expectations with the needs of venture development. Despite these overall advances, only one team identifies a simultaneous improvement in all three components (formalisation, stability, and headcount). Conversely, three teams explicitly report an absence of progress accompanied by team dissolution. These discontinuities indicate that organisational development remains fragile, and that founder alignment is the primary success or failure determinant at this stage: when it breaks, the entrepreneurial journey ends, irrespective of product potential.
- 2) Perceptions of **validation progress** are generally medium and homogeneous across the cohort, but concentrated after the end of iNEST programme, when teams were more exposed to stakeholders. Founders report that first market signals - often in the form of collaborations, interactions, or simple expressions of interest - have supported the refinement of problem-solution fit. At the same time, respondents acknowledge clear boundaries to what validation can achieve within the CCI time horizon. Very early-stage projects, still lacking a functional prototype or even a stable team, struggled to progress beyond elementary testing. Others dropped out simply because the team ceased to exist. The most critical constraint, however, emerges in regulated sectors such as health, where approvals, data access and piloting cycles are intrinsically longer than the Acceleration window. Here founders perceive effort, but little immediately visible outcome.
- 3) Progress in **network development** is sometimes visible but remains modest. Respondents recognise that CCI activated their first contacts with industrial players, experts, and ecosystem actors; however, these interactions have rarely evolved into formal partnerships or commercial pilots within the programme timeframe. In this respect, the Acceleration experience appears capable of opening doors, yet the conversion of those openings into tangible relational capital requires cycles that extend well beyond the duration of the Acceleration Phase.

This dynamic partly reflects a structural limitation of the iNEST model as currently implemented. While the programme offers a rich opportunity space for networking - thanks to the horizontal connections established among participating teams and the vertical interactions with coaches and mentors who could multiply further opportunities - the actual activation of this potential ultimately relies on the proactive behaviour of the start-ups themselves. Building and leveraging a network depends on soft skills, managerial readiness, credibility, and persistence: all elements that are hard to codify and cannot be fully transmitted through workshops alone. In other words, the programme can create favourable context, but it cannot guarantee the birth of stable relationships unless teams are already equipped to recognise, pursue, and follow such opportunities.

As a result, perceived progress in networking tends to be present yet delayed, more strongly

influenced by post-programme continuity mechanisms and by each team's internal relational capabilities than by the activities delivered directly during the Acceleration. This suggests that network development is not merely an output of programme design but a co-produced outcome, contingent on the strategic agency of the venture itself.

- 4) Finally, perceptions of **economic-financial performance** are weak. Many teams report no economic or funding progress, and only a very small number of outliers mention having generated revenue or raised external capital during the programme. This is coherent with the initial immaturity of a significant portion of the cohort, but even more with the strategic focus adopted in the first implementation cycle of CCI, which concentrated resources and mentoring on validation and organisational consolidation. Financial outcomes are therefore expected to lag by design: they can reasonably materialise only once product validation is sufficiently robust and the organisational structure can support investor engagement or market entry.

It should nonetheless be acknowledged that the iNEST Acceleration Phase does include specific activities aimed at stimulating financial readiness. Workshops devoted to business modelling and to understanding external financing mechanisms, together with the Pitch Day, create exposure to potential investors and provide opportunities for early feedback on the economic narrative of the projects. But probably the activation of these opportunities depends on prior progress in the other two dimensions. Without a credible value proposition, a validated use case, and a stable team able to execute it, interactions with investors rarely translate into concrete financial commitments. In this sense, economic-financial performance embodies the end-point of a cumulative process: it cannot advance independently from validation and organisation, but rather emerges once these two foundations cross a minimum viability threshold.

Across these **four domains, a clear pattern** emerges on which teams consider the programme most beneficial. Those entering with an intermediate maturity level, already possessing a cohesive core team, are the ones who most frequently perceive tangible progress in multiple areas. Their organisational foundations have already absorbed the start-up shock, while there remains ample room to grow.

By contrast, high-maturity teams tend to stabilise rather than accelerate, due to programme content that is less aligned with scale-up and investment needs. At the other extreme, very early-stage teams often show little progress not because they lack ambition, but because they fail to keep pace with the cadence and expectations of the Acceleration model. In parallel, some teams with promising maturity profiles stalled abruptly due to internal tensions, underscoring how founder cohesion is a necessary condition for any other outcome.

Sector-specific barriers reinforce this dynamic: when development cycles are structurally long, progress becomes invisible within short observation windows, independently of the real effort invested.

In sum, Round-1 self-reported evidence paints **a picture of sequenced progress**: organisation and validation consolidate first; networking follows but requires longer horizons; financial results emerge only later, and only for those teams that survive and remain aligned.

To facilitate further interpretation and to connect these emerging patterns with established frameworks, the four progress areas considered so far can be synthesised into **three readiness domains**: Validation Readiness (including elements commonly associated with TRL, BRL and CRL), Organisation Readiness, and Investment Readiness (encompassing networking, market scalability, and access to external capital).

This structure aligns with internationally recognised approaches such as the [Innovation Readiness Level™ Model](#) developed by KTH, which stress that meaningful advancement depends on a balanced and simultaneous progression across all readiness dimensions. When development remains skewed - for instance, solid validation but limited organisational cohesion - venture credibility and investor attractiveness are structurally weakened.

Viewed through this readiness lens, the Round-1 findings appear coherent with the **CC1 program focus**, during both the Pre-Acceleration and the Acceleration phase of the two completed rounds.

In fact, using this three readiness domain perspective to review the selection criteria and the workshops contents it appears evident that the program concentrated learning support and evaluative emphasis on Validation, followed by Organisational strengthening, with Investment readiness expected to emerge later and not fully supported by the current offer.

This deliberate orientation partly helps to explain why progress is more visible in concept and team consolidation than in external partnerships or funding outcomes.

Yet the evidence also signals limitations in the current programme architecture: not all teams possess the organisational stability needed to capitalise on validation activities, while ventures operating in long-cycle or highly regulated domains struggle to translate effort into observable milestones within the programme timeframe.

A rebalancing of the workshops' contents towards more significant measures targeted at investment readiness could be beneficial, but not prior to considerations on the minimum inbound maturity level of the teams and on the maximum acceptable heterogeneity level (of sectors / markets, of development stages) of the batches.

Finally, this initial analysis allows a **reflection on the critical admission factors** identified in Chapter 2. Some of these - particularly team size and internal composition / solidity of the teams - continue to show relevance as enablers of progression during Acceleration. Others - such as degree of innovation or sectoral orientation - appear less predictive of short-term outcomes, as sector-specific constraints or slow regulatory pathways may delay visible progress despite strong underlying potential.

Recognising this divergence is essential: it suggests that, in the adopted framework, admission success does not necessarily forecast acceleration success, and that both a refinement of selection criteria (to ensure relevance across all development stages) and complementary support acceleration mechanisms for longer-trajectory ventures or vertical-specific interventions may be needed to better sustain and track progress beyond the entry point.

These insights will directly inform the forward-looking recommendations developed in the next [Chapter](#), where potential evolutions of the CC1 model will be outlined in the attempt to strengthen readiness development and improve the impact of future programmes, or to inspire other innovation ecosystem initiatives in the university and public consortia context.

3.4. Hypotheses verification based on Round 2 data

The Round-2 self-assessment results, although based on fewer respondents and on a shorter observation window (approximately 4-5 months after Demo Day), broadly **confirm the patterns identified in Round 1**. The overall trajectory of progression across Organisation, Validation, Network and Economic-financial dimensions is essentially superimposable to that of the previous batch, suggesting that the dynamics described earlier are not cohort-specific but structural features of the current CC1 model. As a cohort, Round-2 teams also entered the programme from a slightly higher initial quality level, which is consistent with the gradual refinement of scouting and selection processes.

Among the responding teams, perceived progress in Organisation Readiness and Validation Readiness is marginally higher than in Round 1, with some positive deviations in metrics linked to early testing and certification activities. Conversely, Network and Investment dimensions remain comparatively weak, mirroring the earlier evidence that partnership activation and fundraising readiness require longer timeframes and more targeted support than those currently embedded in the Acceleration Phase.

As in Round 1, teams operating in med-tech / life-science domains show distinct behaviour, with slower or less visible progress due to regulatory pathways and validation cycles that extend beyond the programme horizon. Another similar trend is found for a subset of teams entering with medium-high maturity that, again, display near-static trajectories, reinforcing the hypothesis of a “progress plateau” for ventures whose needs exceed the scope of the present acceleration offer, and suggesting that the current programme architecture has limited room for acceleration once a certain threshold of readiness has been achieved.

An element of differentiation between the two cohorts is found in the dropout rate, which appears lower in Round 2, plausibly due to the strengthened coaching mechanism, the introduction of the strategic plan as a unifying guidance tool, and the use of cut-off points to maintain alignment and engagement.

Overall, despite the reduced sample and shorter timeframe, Round-2 data provide a **consistent verification of Round-1 hypotheses**: the programme tends to support organisational consolidation and early validation, while networking and investment readiness remain limited; intermediate-maturity teams benefit the most; and sector-specific constraints, particularly in regulated domains, continue to shape progress visibility.

Conclusions and potential future perspectives

In the previous chapters, the operational modes of the CCI initiative were described, including the Pre-Acceleration process, the evaluation system, and the structure and contents of the Acceleration program. Through the analysis of data collected across all phases, qualitative observations were formulated on key aspects such as:

- the talent engagement extent and potential,
- the characteristics of the applicant projects,
- the critical factors for admission into Acceleration,
- the selection criteria,
- the progress and success of the accelerated teams.

The **aim of this Chapter** is to condense these observations into an overall picture of the value generated by the CCI initiative for the involved actors and stakeholders, and to highlight its main limitations and areas of improvement, providing concrete considerations for future initiatives.

A remark should be made regarding the **scientific limitations** of this report. The analysis is based only on the first two rounds of implementation, whose timeframes are not fully comparable, and the composition of the applicant pool is also somewhat unbalanced toward academic profiles, with limited or no representation of industry-originated initiatives that might face different challenges in validation or fundraising.

These aspects restrict the extent to which findings can be generalised to the broader north-eastern or national innovation ecosystem. In addition, the study is constrained by the size and quality of the available data: the number of observations remains limited, some variables have partial coverage, and the coding of qualitative information inevitably involves a degree of subjectivity.

Likewise, evidence drawn from questionnaires, while insightful, is affected by its qualitative and self-reported nature.

For these reasons, the results and recommendations presented here should be interpreted as indicative of emerging patterns and tendencies in academic early-stage startup contexts, rather than as statistically generalisable conclusions.

Main observations

As for the **talent engagement extent and potential**, universities showed different levels of activity through their Scouting Specialists, yet collectively attracted a wide and diverse set of talents from the territories, including external participants. Targeted scouting efforts (towards researchers and professors) were more quality-oriented and effective than Open Calls, and a progression was observed from smaller teams in Round 1 (1–2 members) to more robust and complementary teams in Round 2 (3–5 members).

Going into detail about the **characteristics of the applicant projects**, there was a high concentration of projects in specific macro-themes such as *Smart Industries*, *Cultural and Creative Industries*, and *Health Tech and Services*. Most relied on “soft” and non-patented technologies, with innovation mainly incremental and frequent uncertainty on intellectual-property protection strategy and measures.

Moving on to the **critical factors for admission into Acceleration**, projects in sectors such as *Smart Industries* and *Health* appeared to enter Acceleration more easily; intermediate team size (3–5 members), solid academic grounding and some degree of innovation were also favorable conditions. A review of the **selection criteria** potential biases and effectiveness pointed out they were slightly skewed toward technical robustness and business and market readiness, and not fully integrated with the structure and contents of the Acceleration program.

Finally, considering the **progress and success of the accelerated teams**, strongest progress was observed in Organisational development, followed by Validation; Network and Economic-Financial advancements were smaller.

Teams of intermediate maturity tended to benefit most, while the least mature struggled to keep pace and the most advanced tended to stabilise rather than accelerate.

To this regard, a review of the selection criteria and of the workshops' contents revealed a marked emphasis of the CCI program on Validation and Organisational support, with Investment readiness expected to emerge later and not fully supported by the current offer.

This was a deliberate orientation of the initiative but at the same time a limitation of its architecture, in addition to providing a generalist, time-boxed Acceleration path to highly heterogeneous cohorts.

Value and legacy of the CCI initiative

The iNEST CCI experience achieved the establishment of an unprecedented innovation-support structure in the Italian north-eastern ecosystem, remarkable for its scale, diversity of players, and coherent integration of resources. The specific value delivered, and its legacy, can be summarised in four main contributions:

1. **Operational and coordination network:** creation of new relationships and a synergic intervention model among nine universities and their affiliated entities, enabling shared governance and a coordinated operative intervention.
2. **Methodologies:** development of standardised processes and tools for target engagement, data collection, evaluation and selection of projects, program management, communication, and promotion.
3. **Offer:** delivery of an integrated package of entrepreneurial training, plus a coaching service, a toolbox and networking opportunities, tailored to research-driven start-ups.
4. **External network:** establishment of first connections with local companies for open-innovation collaborations and with financial operators specialised in early-stage research-based ventures.

Limitations of the CCI initiative

Despite these achievements, some structural limitations emerged such as the **partial misalignment** between the evaluation system and the Acceleration contents, reducing the coherence between how start-ups are selected and what they later receive as support. Considering the Acceleration strategy itself, a **time-boxed Acceleration model** proved challenging for highly heterogeneous batches (both in market focus and maturity level). Moreover, **underdeveloped support measures for networking and fundraising** limited the teams' ability to convert validation into investment readiness (see [Appendix B](#) for more information on the CCI Open Innovation and Fundraising measures, complementary to Acceleration).

Operational recommendations for future initiatives

Building on the insights presented across chapters, and in line with internationally recognised frameworks such as the [Innovation Readiness Level™ Model](#) developed by KTH, future initiatives could benefit from the following directions:

- **Cross-stage coherence:** refine selection criteria so they remain meaningful throughout all programme stages, enabling consistent tracking of progress and success.
- **Evaluation and monitoring systems:** adopt readiness-level models (covering validation, organisation, and investment) to ensure balanced progress in all areas, and connect assessment metrics directly to Acceleration workshops and mentoring activities.
- **Cohort design and tailored / modular Acceleration tracks:** reduce heterogeneity through better clustering of start-ups by maturity or sector; introduce modular, opt-in programme

components; consider non-time-boxed or personalised pathways that allow differentiated progression speeds.

- **Strengthening market orientation and investment readiness:** expand the networking and fundraising components, reinforce investor-relation modules, and foster partnerships with companies and financial actors.

For what concerns the acceleration stage, for instance, the support tracks may **distinguish venture stages**, e.g. (i) idea/concept validation initiatives from (ii) Problem-Solution-Fit to Product-Market-Fit initiatives. Needs in fact are very different for teams with TRL4 and below, who have not yet matched their ideas or their Proof of Concepts (PoCs) capabilities versus teams who have already validated those concepts with early adopters, but that are plateauing revenue streams.

Then, on the sectoral orientation side, even though the overlaying set of competencies necessary to a start-up rely on a common baseline, specific aspects apply to various market vertical aggregations. Hence there might be an opportunity to provide **vertical specific** nuances e.g. for life science initiatives (health, med-tech, agri/food tech) requiring strict regulatory compliance, IP protection and licensing agreements vs sustainability initiatives (more tied to ESG, or nature positive impact) or AI native ones.

Sustainability and continuation outlook

Regarding the **strategic and operational sustainability** of CC1, the Committee proposed a lighter yet effective structure to ensure continuity beyond the initial funding phase. This model foresees one overall coordinator, three regional representatives, and one operational contact within each participating institution (among the active profiles from existing Technology Transfer or Research Valorisation Offices) to guarantee strategic alignment and day-to-day operability. **Financial sustainability** could rely on joint support from regional and provincial administrations, internal contributions from universities (including in-kind resources), and the involvement of private partners, such as Venture Capital funds, to strengthen the bridge between public research and the market.

This continuation model would preserve the collaborative foundation built by CC1 while enabling gradual consolidation and adaptation.

The lessons learned from these first two implementation cycles, both in design and execution, provide a robust basis for refining future Acceleration programmes within iNEST and beyond, ensuring that regional innovation ecosystems evolve toward more integrated, effective, and sustainable forms of research-driven entrepreneurship support.

Beyond the implementation perspective, **future research avenues** may focus on: longitudinal monitoring of Round 2 teams to verify medium-term effects; comparison between time-boxed Acceleration paths and more flexible or vertical paths; updating readiness indicators to include organisational, regulatory and investment dimensions.

Appendices

A. Selection and evaluation criteria

Program phase	Criteria (each on a 1 to 5 evaluation scale)
Pre-Acc, Acc	1. Problem identification and relevance
Pre-Acc, Acc	2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit
Pre-Acc, Acc	3. Solution novelty
Pre-Acc, Acc	4. Intellectual property (IP) protection
Pre-Acc, Acc	5. Social and environmental impact
Pre-Acc, Acc	6. Addressable market
Pre-Acc, Acc	7. Market competitiveness and positioning
Pre-Acc, Acc	8. Team commitment and execution capability
Pre-Acc, Acc	9. Business model effectiveness and solidity
Pre-Acc, Acc	10. Operating model scalability
Acc	11. Go to market / Action plan

For each criterion we report here the detailed description of the five scoring levels.

1. Problem identification & relevance

1 (Not Relevant) The problem addressed is unclear or insignificant, with no demand for a solution.

2 The problem addressed is somewhat defined but there isn't evident demand for a solution.

3 (Moderately Relevant) The problem addressed is clearly and relevant, showing a evident demand for solution.

4 The problem addressed is widespread, affecting a significant minority of the people, with a strong demand for a solution.

5 (Critically Relevant) The problem addressed is universal, affecting a vast majority of the people, with a strong and urgent demand for a solution.

2. Idea definition and problem-solution fit

1 (No Fit) The idea is poorly defined and/or there isn't a problem-solution fit

2 The idea is somewhat defined and there is a somewhat clear problem-solution fit

3 (Moderate Fit) The idea is clearly defined and there is a good problem-solution fit

4 The idea is clearly defined and there is a very good problem-solution fit

5 (Strong Fit) The idea is outstanding as well as the problem-solution fit

3. Solution novelty

1 (Minimal Innovation) The solution offers little to no innovation, closely resembling existing products or services with no distinct advantages.

2 The solution shows some innovation, offering slight improvements or changes to existing products or services.

3 (Moderate Innovation) The solution is moderately innovative, introducing new features to existing products or services, efficiencies, or addressing the problem in a new way.

4 The solution is highly innovative, significantly advancing the current state of the art or employing a novel approach to solve the problem.

5 (Groundbreaking Innovation) The solution represents a breakthrough, redefining existing paradigms or creating entirely new markets with its innovative approach.

4. Intellectual Property (IP) Protection

1 (No IP protection) The startup's core know-how or technology is inherently difficult to protect due to its generic nature or lack of distinctiveness. There's a significant challenge in establishing clear IP rights.

2 The startup possesses some unique know-how or technology, yet faces challenges in IP protection due to restrictive IP laws or the nature of the innovation, making it hard to fully secure exclusive rights.

3 (Partial IP protection) The startup's unique know-how or technology is partially protectable through non-patent strategies such as trade secrets, design rights and copyrights. This provides a basic level of IP protection that may require additional strategies to strengthen.

4 The startup's unique know-how or technology is well-protected with enforceable IP rights, including trademarks, trade secrets, design protections and copyrights. These rights effectively safeguard the startup's competitive position.

5 (Full IP protection) The startup's unique know-how or technology enjoys comprehensive IP protection, including patents, trademarks, trade secrets, design protections or copyrights. This extensive IP portfolio not only secures the startup's innovations but also significantly enhances its valuation and attractiveness to investors.

5. Social and Environmental Impact

1 (Minimal Impact) The startup shows little to no focus on social or environmental impact.

2 The startup has a nominal focus on social or environmental impact, but it is not central to the business model or operations.

3 (Average Impact) The startup demonstrates a moderate level of commitment to making a positive social or environmental impact, with some integration into its business model.

4 The startup is strongly committed to social and environmental impact, with clear strategies and actions integrated into its core operations.

5 (Significant Impact) The startup is at the forefront of social and environmental impact, with innovative approaches and significant, measurable outcomes central to its mission.

6. Addressable market

1 (Small Mkt) The addressable market is poorly defined or non-existent, there is a little to no potential for growth

2 The addressable market is somehow defined, there is a significant knowledge gap regarding size and demographics of potential customers and a little potential for growth

3 (Medium Mkt) The addressable market is reasonably defined but highly competitive, there is some understanding of potential customers and some potential for growth

4 The addressable market is well-defined, there is a solid understanding of potential customers and a potential for growth, also through differentiation

5 (Large Mkt) The addressable market is well-defined and highly attractive, there is a large and growing demand in the sector and a clear opportunity for growth

7. Market Competitiveness and Positioning

1 (Weak CA) The startup has no clear competitive advantage, with poor market positioning that makes it vulnerable to competition.

2 The startup has a slight competitive advantage but struggles with differentiation or faces strong competition.

3 (Average CA) The startup is competitively positioned with a clear value proposition, though it faces notable competition.

4 The startup has a strong competitive advantage, good market positioning, and strategies to maintain or enhance its market status.

5 (Strong CA) The startup is a market leader or has a disruptive competitive advantage, with exceptional positioning that sets it apart from all competitors.

8. Team Commitment and Execution Capability

1 (Weak) The team lacks commitment, relevant skills, or experience necessary to execute the business plan effectively.

2 The team shows some commitment and has relevant skills but lacks comprehensive experience or cohesion.

3 (Average) The team has a balanced mix of skills and experience, with a reasonable level of commitment and the capability to execute the business plan.

4 The team is highly committed, with strong, relevant skills and a proven track record of execution in relevant fields.

5 (Strong) The team demonstrates exceptional commitment, diverse expertise, outstanding leadership, and a clear ability to execute complex business plans successfully.

9. Business Model Effectiveness and Solidity

1 (Undefined BM) The startup's business model is unclear and untested, with no evident path to profitability. It lacks detailed plans for revenue generation and cost management.

2 The business model is outlined but lacks depth in adaptability. It shows potential for revenue but needs refinement to ensure long-term viability and competitiveness.

3 (Defined BM) The startup has a business model with a clear revenue stream and cost structure. It's viable in the current market but may require adjustments for significant growth or market shifts.

4 The business model is robust, designed to support growth. It includes strategies for expansion, cost efficiency, and maintaining competitive advantage, showing adaptability to market changes.

5 (Innovative BM) The startup's business model is a core asset: offering market resilience, and a clear competitive edge, it is well-prepared for rapid growth, market leadership, and long-term success.

10. Operating model scalability

1 (Limited) The operating model has significant barriers to scalability, since it is highly capital and labour intensive or, more generally, it faces high costs and/or operational challenges.

2 The scalability of the operating model is possible, since it is average capital and labour intensive, but challenging due to operational inefficiencies.

3 (Average) The operating model shows potential for scalability, with some identified paths to overcome operational constraints.

4 The operating model has a clear, viable path to scalability, since it is supported by digital processes.

5 (Extensive) The operating model is highly scalable, since it is totally digitalized.

11. Go to market / Action plan

1 (Naive) G2M/A Plan is naive or non-existent, lacking clear strategies for sourcing, distribution, and customer acquisition

2 G2M/A Plan is basic, presents elements for product introduction and customer outreach, lacks depth in execution

3 (Solid, clear) Solid understanding of targets and channels, clear tactics for reaching customers and enabling organisational drivers

4 G2M/A Plan is comprehensive and well-developed, incorporating innovative strategies for market entry, customer and organisational engagement

5 (Highly sophisticated) G2M/A Plan is highly sophisticated, leveraging existing supply and distribution channels and insights to achieve market penetration and organisational maturity

B. Open Innovation and Fundraising activities within iNEST CC1

The iNEST CC1 program included a first attempt of ideation and implementation of Open Innovation and Fundraising activities to be conducted at multi-regional level and offered to the highly heterogeneous batches of accelerated startups.

The **Open Innovation track** was led by University of Udine with the aim of exploring the Triveneto companies system, establishing first contacts and potentially facilitating matchmaking between CC1 start-ups and companies.

The activity progressed in four main steps:

1. Study of Open Innovation best practices in academia
2. Mapping of companies in the North-East of Italy, to identify the most innovation-oriented ones, and massive pre-screening of propensity to innovate based on balance sheet data (quantitative)
3. Evaluation of the pre-screened companies with innovation indicators and engagement of the most innovative ones in the "Open Innovation Day" event
4. Semi-structured 1-1 interviews with a subset of the previously identified most innovative companies.

For the **mapping**, Bureau Van Dijke's AIDA software was chosen, as it allows for the easy processing of Italian companies' financial statement data. A pre-screening of 285422 companies was conducted, considering all limited companies in the three iNEST regions, without size restrictions, and filtering on balance sheet data related to innovation propensity.

Then the **selection** was restricted to companies with turnover higher than 50 M€. The remaining 350 companies were further evaluated based on balance sheet items considered relevant by academic literature for the purpose of identifying innovation performance, including input and output indicators of the innovation process (mainly in relation to the following voices: R&D costs; patents; Return on Assets (ROA)).

The ranked companies were also clustered according to iNEST Macro themes, regional Smart Specialisation Strategies and Pavitt's Taxonomy.

For the top 60 companies an in-depth company card was created, leading to a final selection of 40 companies to be invited to the "**Open Innovation Day**" and awarded for their innovativeness.

The event constituted the first occasion of public exposure and dissemination of the CC1 initiative goals and activities towards an initial group of innovative companies, with which to prime potential collaborations Start-ups - Company collaborations and/or University - Company collaborations.

Subsequently, a series of **interviews** was designed to build closer relationships with the identified companies and to better highlight the intersections between their innovation trajectories and the development paths of the pre-accelerated and accelerated CC1 startup projects.

The specific purpose of the interviews was to qualitatively understand how the innovativeness of the interviewed companies manifests and what strategies underpin their success.

The semi-structured interview format was chosen to allow interviewees to speak freely, avoiding overly direct or closed questions, therefore instructing the interviewers to ask open-ended questions and use follow-ups to explore in-depth and, if a relevant theme naturally arises, to avoid redundancy with other structured questions.

The interviews had the following outline of themes to be addressed:

- Business model and positioning
- Product and process innovation
- Innovation in services and digitalisation
- Collaborative ecosystem and co-innovation
- Measurement and governance of innovation
- Sustainability and connection with the local area.

The conversations were recorded and transcribed with the interviewee's prior authorization. The collected material was stored exclusively for research purposes.

To date, seven interviews have been completed, summarised and analysed to extract insights for guiding potential future collaboration activities. The activity should be continued and strengthened to effectively favour the matching of companies with startups, as a complement to pre-acceleration and acceleration programmes.

The **Fundraising track** was led by University of Trieste and Polo Tecnologico Alto Adriatico with the aim of supporting all the accelerated startups in getting familiar with terminology and dynamics for startup funding, and assisting them in meeting their financial needs by developing a fundraising network, identifying and engaging potential investors and providing guidance in negotiating and structuring investment deals.

The track involved the selection of external specialists and experts that could further assess the startup investment readiness and guided the most promising early stage start-ups in adopting the most effective approaches to fundraising, conducive to their transition into scale-ups.

The activity unfolded in six complementary areas:

1. **Introduction to banking:** training cycle on financial instruments, banking terminology and how to access credit
2. **Meetings with banks:** direct meetings with credit institutions to facilitate access to loans and credit lines dedicated to innovative start-ups
3. **Speed dating and meetings with entrepreneurs:** opportunities to meet and exchange ideas with successful entrepreneurs
4. **Legal sanity check:** on demand check-up and feedback by a legal expert (University of Padua Full Professor of Commercial Law and Industrial and New Technology Law), covering: Corporate structure and governance, Company incorporation, Intellectual property, Contracts, Legal risk management, Legal and ethical aspects of the use of artificial intelligence
5. **Investment readiness assessment and strategy:** 1-1 consultancy meetings for both an assessment of the startup preparedness and offering advice on defining investment strategies and preparing for dialogue with investors
6. **Venture Day:** final showcase event for the CC1 initiative, targeted at territorial representatives, policymakers and, especially, leading Italian players in Venture Capital and early-stage investment (including VC funds and business angels). The event brought together start-ups from both the first and second cycle of the CC1 and provided them with the opportunity to have 1-1 meetings with potential funding partners, reinforcing the role of the program in bridging the gap between acceleration and market entry.

Regarding the **1-1 fundraising consultancy** for the CC1 accelerated startups, the investment readiness assessment focused on the following aspects of fundamental interest to investors: team, market, timing (of the solution w.r.t. the market), competitive advantage, scalability, exit strategy.

Of the 30 accelerated startups, 20 were met by the consultant, who evidenced a general difficulty of the teams to develop a real entrepreneurial conviction, even if they made significant efforts to explore the validity of their original technical idea / solution and took the first steps into business readiness.

Some of the initiatives analysed were deemed too “immature”, with teams that were not sufficiently structured and, although they showed interesting potential, not all of them were considered ready to interact with external investors in the short term. About ten initiatives were found to be adequately structured and ready to hold preliminary discussions with venture capital operators.

The final **Venture Day** session represented a key moment of discussion and visibility for start-ups, while also allowing valuable information to be gathered on market interests. The session was attended by five institutional investors⁷ with complementary profiles, representing different segments of the Italian innovation ecosystem.

The presence of players with different experiences and interests contributed to creating a varied discussion, offering start-ups the opportunity to test their proposals in front of interlocutors with different perspectives, from institutional investors to corporate investors and business angel networks.

To facilitate communication between start-ups and investors and to ease contacts and mutual understanding between the parties involved, the investment players were asked to provide a short bio while the start-ups were asked to share, in addition to the pitch deck, a one pager presentation of their project containing the most significant information about: Business description; Product/Service (indicating the TRL); Market and Competition; Business Model; Team; Results achieved; Key next steps; Capital to be raised; Use of funds to be raised; Revenue and Cost Estimates for the coming years; Exit strategy; Expectation from the meeting with investors.

There were 16 formal individual meetings lasting 30 minutes each and the interactions with investors, including the informal ones, showed general curiosity and gave startups a first opportunity to interact directly with investment operators.

The consultancy team will provide further availability and support to startups in discussing the outcomes of the meetings and organising the next steps, while, in parallel, establishing and consolidating contacts with additional investors.

This activity represents an important strategic step in ensuring that start-ups gradually begin to appear on the radar of the investor ecosystem. From this perspective, preliminary contact with selected investors increases the visibility of the companies involved and lays the foundations for potential collaboration or investment opportunities in the medium term.

⁷ IAG (Italian Angels for Growth), Vesper Holding, Growth Capital, ZNext (Zanichelli Venture), Obloo Ventures